

CHAPTER-V

DATA INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS

The present chapter discusses the results of the study with regard to perception of the tourism academicians and tourism industry professionals regarding quality of tourism education in India. Tourism academicians of State and Central universities across the country are the part of the discussion while tourism professionals of Indian Association of Tour Operators (IATO) have been brought under the discussion of the chapter. The data have been collected from online questionnaire. The sample of 129 (each) respondents from tourism academia as well as tourism professionals has been received. There are two different questionnaires one for tourism academicians and another tourism professionals.

Among tourism academicians, the data collected from Professors, Associate Professors, Assistant Professors, Guest Faculty and Research Scholars. The entire questionnaire (for academicians) has been divided into six parts which are: A. General Information about the institute and academicians, B. Programme Information C. Course frame work and Infrastructure D. Students' Profile in the Institute E. Skill Development after the Course Completion F. Opinion on Tourism Education. A set of fifty seven questions has been asked from these respondents.

Among the asked questions, three are dichotomous, four open ended questions and thirty two questions are based on 5 point Likert scale and the rest are multiple choice based and check box type questions. The questionnaire responded by the tourism academicians has been attached as Appendix in thesis. The respondents are from 74 public universities which are providing tourism education in the country. There was at least one respondent from each organisation.

Similarly, the entire questionnaire (for tourism professionals) has been divided into six parts which are: A. Company Information B. Services offered by company C. Employee's Profile D. Employee capability at the time of hiring E. Opinion on Tourism Education. A set of seventy questions has been asked from these respondents. Among the asked questions, two are dichotomous, five open ended questions and forty five question are based on 5 point Likert scale and the rest are multiple choice based and check box type questions. The questionnaire responded by

the tourism professionals has been attached as Appendix in the thesis. There are 86 travel companies which provided the responses for research work, at least one response from each company. As indicated in chapter three, surveys of respondents generated 258 complete and valid questionnaires, which are equally distributed as tourism academicians (129) and tourism industry professionals (129).

5.1 Institutional Information

This part of study shows the percentage distribution of respondents in regards to designation and department affiliation. It asserts the opinions of academicians and tourism professionals. With regard to academicians the data collected about designation, department affiliation, infrastructure availability and years of teachings. In addition to precedent parameters data are collected about existence of different departments in tourism professionals' organisation.

5.1.1) Designation

It shows the percentage of respondents from academia and tourism industry with regards to designation.

a) Academicians

Chart 5.1: Percentage of respondents among tourism academicians.

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Chart 5.1 shows the majority of the respondents are Assistant professor i.e. 33.3 percent of total respondents.

b) Tourism professionals

Chart 5.2 shows the strata of respondents (Tourism Professionals) across the Top, Middle and Lower management. The designation of respondents varies from Chief Executive Officer to executive trainee, Managing Director to management trainee, and travel consultant to product development. The low level management has majority of respondents i.e. 45 percent.

Chart 5.2: The percentage of distribution among respondents from tourism industry

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

5.1.2) Departmental affiliation

The department affiliation of tourism professionals and academicians is discussed in this part of study.

a1) Academicians

Table 5.1 talks about the affiliation of the department whether it is a complete discipline in itself or is being disciplined by other department.

Table 5.1: Department affiliation (academicians)

Sr. No.	Departmental affiliation	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Independent department	81	62.8
2	Under Management Faculty	23	17.8
3	Under Commerce Faculty	10	7.8
4	Under Commerce and Management Faculty	7	5.4
5	Under Arts Faculty	8	6.2
6	Total	129	100.0

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Among total academic respondents, 62.8% (which is highest) respondents opined that they have tourism department as independent discipline.

b1) Department affiliation-tourism professionals

C 5.1 reveals that, the percentage of respondents from Marketing and Sales (22.48), Operation (11.62) and Management (10.07) are leading departments' share. The MICE (Meetings, Incentives, Conferences and Events) department is new but has established itself as department. The Inbound, Outbound, Corporate even though Logistics, Adventure, Human Resource, Domestic and Reservation (Flight/Accommodation) department are among the other affiliated department of respondents.

Graph 5.1: Department affiliation

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

b2) Different departments in respondents' travel organisation

The frequency of responses of tourism professionals regarding the specified department in existing companies are as Operation 119, Accounts 111, Marketing/sales 109, Transportation 79, Product Development 78, Human Resource (HR) 64, Quality Control, Research and Analysis 50 and non-respondents have no specified departments.

Image 5.1: Specific departments

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

*largest size of words depict the largest percentage/frequency

b3) Typology of tourism business and operations (tourism professionals)

Table 5.2 shows the typology of business practiced by more than 50 percent of respondents are Business to Consumer (B2C). It was also found that there are 54.3 percent respondents work for tour operator.

Table 5.2: Typology/operation

Type of Tourism Business			Type of operation		
	Frequency	Percent		Frequency	Percent
B2B	42	32.6	TO	70	54.3
B2C	65	50.4	TA	48	37.2
B2B, B2C	22	17.1	TO,TA	11	8.5
Total	129	100.0	Total	129	100.0

Source: Primary data through questionnaire

TO: Tour Operator TA: Travel Agent, B2B- Business to business, B2C-Business to Consumer

5.1.3) Year of teaching and year of service in industry

It was tried to investigate, for how long majority of the respondents i.e. academicians and tourism professionals are serving either in academia and tourism industry respectively.

Table 5.3: Teaching/service experience

Years of teaching	Tourism Academicians	Tourism professionals
<5	54.3	53.5
6-10	14.7	16.3
11-15	10.9	9.3
16-20	9.3	7.8
>20	10.9	13.2
Total	100.0	100.0

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Table 5.4 points out that majority of respondents are having teaching or industry experience <5 years. It shows that tourism education is new discipline and tourism industry is industry of young professionals.

5.1.4) Infrastructure availability in the department of academic respondent

Table 5.4 clearly reveals the status of existing infrastructure in the institutions providing tourism education.

Table 5.4: Infrastructure availability

Sr. No.	Facilities for students	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Computer Lab	94	72.87
2.	Placement Cell	93	72.09
3.	Departmental Library/ Internet-Wi-Fi	92	71.72
4.	Smart Classroom(s)/ Newspaper	91	70.54
5.	Tourism Journal	83	64.34
6.	Tourism Magazine	82	63.57
7.	Tourism Software	44	34.12
8.	Tourism Newspaper/ Student Support Cell	20	15.50

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

With Regards to student support cell: The cell is established with the objectives to motivate students towards academic excellence, extracurricular and co-curricular activities participation, psychological support and guest lecturer (Bharti Vidyapeeth, 2019). While, Indian Institute of Management, Kashipur (2019), established such cell to conduct mock interview, group discussion (maximize performance, opinion presentation in group environment, Dos and Don'ts), Preparatory Session (Industry, Market and Curriculum Vitae analysis) and Information Sharing (reading material and company background and analysis). In context of tourism education institutions only 15.50 percent of respondents mentioned about its existence in the department.

With regard to digital platform in the department: Digital platform has given a change to diversify tourism product (Dredge et al., 2019). The result shows that only 34.12 percent of respondents have accepted the 'tourism software' training in the department. The facilities regarding 'computer lab' and departmental 'internet' are also lacking.

With regards to Library resources: Library is the heart of an institution (Arjun et al., 2010). It was found that a considerable percentage of respondents' institute are not providing 'tourism world information environment'.

5.2 Specialisation Offered

It discusses about the opinions of both i.e. tourism academicians and tourism professionals on specialization offered and type of specialization education/services offered.

a1) Specialisation based tourism education programs offered or not (Academicians)

The 21st century is a knowledge based economy (OECD, 2016) and its demands specialised knowledge. It was found that a big number of tourism education institutes are providing specialised programs.

Chart 5.3: Any specialisation?

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Among the 129 respondents 60.5 % responded positively i.e. their institute provide specialisation based tourism education.

a2) Specialisation based tourism education programs offered

Table 5.5 shows the specialization of tourism programs offered in India, are general in nature and specialisation programs as per the demand of economy are near absent in Indian education system. The majority of academicians show that specialization based tourism education being provided in the country. But, the research has also shown that Travel and Tourism Management, Tourism and Hospitality Management and Tourism Management are dominating the Indian tourism education system.

Table 5.5: Specialization offered by institutions

Sr. No.	Specialization offered	Specialization offered
1.	Accounts and Tourism	Tour Operation, Airline Ticketing, Cargo Management, Event Management
2.	Adventure and Gastronomy Tourism	Tour operation, marketing, HR, Finance
3.	Adventure Tourism	Tour Operations / Event Management
4.	Adventure, Events, Travel Trade and Air Ticketing	Tourism
5.	Air Fares and Ticketing	Tourism
6.	Airlines, Tourism and Hospitality	Tourism
7.	Aviation Management and Event Management	Tourism and Hospitality
8.	Aviation Management and Event Management	Tourism and Hospitality
9.	Culinary Arts and tourism	Tourism and Hospitality
10.	Cultural Tourism	Tourism and Hospitality
11.	Diploma in Medical Tourism	Tourism and Hospitality Management
12.	Tourism Services	Tourism and airlines
13.	Tourism and history	Tourism and hospitality
14.	Tourism and hospitality	Tourism and Hotel Management
15.	General MBA(Tourism) and Cargo	Tourism and Skills
16.	HM, Tourism Marketing, Tourism Entrepreneurship and Tourism Management	Tourism and Travel disciplines
17.	History and tourism	Tourism and Travel Management
18.	Hotel and Tourism Management	Tourism management
19.	In Hospitality and Tourism	Tourism management
20.	Inbound tourism and Outbound tourism as Major and Adventure tourism and Event Management as Minor	Tourism Management
21.	Master of Tourism Management	Tourism Management Sustainable Development
22.	MBA (T) HR and Marketing, BBA (tourism), and integrated BHMCT and MHMCT	Tourism Studies
23.	MBA BBA PhD	Tourism Management
24.	MBA BBA PhD	Travel and Tourism
25.	MBA Tourism	Travel and Tourism Management
26.	MBA Tourism, PG Diploma in Tourism	Travel and Tourism Management
27.	MBA Tourism, PG Diploma in Tourism	Travel and tourism
28.	Rural Tourism	Travel and tourism
29.	Sustainable Tourism	Travel and tourism management

30.	Sustainable tourism	Travel and Tourism with Travel Agency and Tour Operations
31.	Teach French, Industrial visits	Travel and Tourism, Hospitality Operation
32.	Tour operation	Travel trade
33.	Tour operation	Travel trade, marketing, cargo management and event management
34.	Tour Packaging operation, Event Management	

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

*51.93 per cent of respondents mentioned the name of the specialization.

The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) has put forward that world economy which is knowledge-based i.e. technology, information and high level of skill are required in a knowledge-based economy and organisations are building networks to acquire specialized knowledge (OECD, 2016). It implies that Skills can be acquired through specialised programs, which are near to absent in Indian tourism education system. Hence, the knowledge based economy give rise to the demand for incorporation of specialization based tourism courses i.e. Tourism and Data Mining, Tourism and Sustainable Development, Rural Tourism, Tourism and Digital Marketing, Tourism and Data analytics, Tourism and Technology.

b1) Specialised services offered or not (tourism professionals)

Among the 129 respondents 79.1 per cent respondents opined that their tourism organisations offer specialized services.

Chart 5.4: Any specialisation?

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

b2) Opinion of tourism professionals about specialized services offered by respondent being a tourism professional

Graph 5.2 shows that during research that travel companies are focused on specialization based tourism services. As per the percentage of responses collected through open ended question was dominated by MICE (13.95), Adventure Tourism (10.85) and Special Interest Tourism (12.40).

Graph 5.2: Specialized services offered a tourism professional

Destination based tourism packages or continent based tourism services are growing. Adventure tourism, MICE, Experiential Tourism, Product Development. Medical Events, off Beat Tourism training and learning are growing Specialization in the tourism industry.

b3) Nature of specialized services offered in respondents' organisation (Tourism professionals)

It was tried to know through 'closed-options' about 'Nature of specialized services offered by organisation', the responses are as Leisure Tourism (85.27 %), MICE (48.84%), Conferencing (45.74%), School Tours (42.64%), Business (Trade Fare) (41.09%), Chartered Cruise Services (32.56%) and Visa Specialization (25.58%). Image show larger the size of word have more frequency than the word smallest in size.

Image 5.1.1: Name of specialized services

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

*largest size of words depict the largest percentage/frequency

5.3 Program Information

This part discusses the opinion of respondents i.e. academicians about nature of tourism course offered, general course components and tourism course components. It also studies about the perception of tourism professionals in regard to ‘must require’ skills from tourism graduates, typology of business/operation, services offered by their travel-trade company and participation in tourism education promotions.

a1) Nature of tourism courses offered (Academicians)

The word cloud image 5.2 shows, Tourism courses are offered as Certificate, Diploma, and Graduation, Post-Graduation, and Integrated Post graduation, Integrated MPhil cum PhD, MPhil and PhD. The image shows the largest size of ‘PhD’ and smallest by ‘MPhil’. It was found that among 129 respondents, 55.81 (72 respondents) percent have mentioned that PhD Course is taught in their department. The Undergraduate and Post-graduation by 52 respondents, Post-graduation by 43 respondents, Under graduation by 28 respondents, Diploma by 36 respondents, Certificate by 13 respondents, MPhil cum PhD by 6 respondents and MPhil 3 by respondents.

Image 5.2: Nature of tourism courses

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

*UG-PG Integrated Under Graduation and Post-graduation,**MPhil-PhD: Integrated Master of Philosophy cum Doctor of Philosophy. *largest size of words depict the largest percentage/frequency

a2) General course components that are included in the tourism programs (academicians)

The image shows the 'general course components' that are included in the tourism programs. These components are Management, Accountancy, Finance, Statistics, Research Methodology, Economics, Environment Science, Geography, Information Technology, Information technology (Digital marketing/application development/Augmented reality) and Data Mining. Moreover, Human resource behaviour and organisational behaviour (HRB-OB), Personality development, business communication, communicative skills and entrepreneurship were added by respondents as additional component. Data mining was considered by the respondents in term of statistics instead of technological progression. Information technology (Digital marketing/application development/Augmented reality) component has only theoretical use not practical. Because there is no specialized program in tourism education. Management, Research Methodology and Geography are part of general course component of tourism program with response rate 87.59 %, 79.07% and 72.09 % respectively. The percentage for Information Technology, Accountancy, Economics, Finance, Environment Science and Statistics is 58.91, 55.03, 52.71, 47.23, 42.64 and 34.88 respectively.

Image 5.3: General course components that are included in the tourism programs

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

*EVS (Environment Science), HRB-OB-(Human resource behaviour-organizational behaviour)

*IT Advance- Information technology (Digital marketing/application development/Augmented reality),

*largest size of words depict the largest percentage/frequency

a3) Tourism course component with regard to tourism industry (academicians)

Image 5.4 shows the number of respondents with respect to the question that ‘ what are tourism specific components included in the tourism program (s)’. It shows the higher frequency words as bigger in size than having low frequency. The percentage of disciplines which are responded by at least more than 62.02 percent; Travel Agents and Tour Operators (TAO) (91.47 %), Accommodation (75.19%), Tourism Research (68.99%), Tourism Policy (68.21%), Airlines and Cargo Management (ACM) (67.44%), Event Management (67.44%), and On the Job Training (OJT) (65.11 %).

Image 5.4: Tourism course component in tourism programs

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

*DM-destination management, OA-outdoor activities, HRM-Human resource management, MICE-Meeting, Incentives, Conferencing and Exhibition, TSA-Travel Software application, MIS-management Information System, CRM-Computerised Reservation System.*largest size of words depict the largest percentage/frequency

5.4 Students' Profile and Employees' Profile

It was discussed here about the opinion of tourism academicians about educational, schooling, origin of students and dropout rate pursuing tourism programs. The opinion of tourism professionals about precedent parameters analysed with regard to tourism employees also.

a1) Educational background of students

The chart indicates the educational background of the students in Tourism Education programs.

Chart 5.5: Educational Background

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

The majority of respondents opined that 46.0 per cent students have educational background from Arts discipline.

a2) Schooling Background of students

The question is based on three categories- whether the students come from Private Institution, Government Institution or Correspondence mode of education.

Chart 5.6: Schooling of students

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

It was investigated that 56.6 percent academicians have opinion that the enrollment in tourism programs from government institution pass out students is higher than others.

a3) Origin of students for admission in tourism programs

The origin of students, which means whether the students come from the native State of institution or from other States. The data shows, 65.1 percent academicians have mentioned that majority of students in tourism programs are come from native State where tourism education institute established (Chart-5.7). Although, Clayton (2019), has mentioned that pursuing a course outside the comfort zone leads to, understanding of different cultures, experiences, better equipped to enter the wider world, open-minded personality, curious and accepting.

Chart 5.7: Origin of student

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

b1) Educational background of the employees, in respondents’ travel trade organisation

It was studied through table 5.6 that majority of tourism professionals (40.3 percent) have opined that employees in their organisation have tourism educational background.

Table 5.6: Educational of employees

Educational background	Arts	Commerce	Science	Management	Tourism	IT
Percentage	13.2	12.4	3.1	27.9	40.3	3.1

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

b2) Origin of the employees, in respondents’ travel trade organisation

Table 5.7 shows, the majority of tourism professionals (50.4 percent) have opined that employees in their organisation have origin from ‘within and outside State(s)’.

Table 5.7: Origin of the employees

Origin of employees	Mostly Same State	Mostly Other State(S)	Both
Percentage	35.7	14.0	50.4

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

5.5 Crosstab Analysis of Opinions of Academicians across Dropout Rate, Origin and Schooling Background; Dropout Rate and Educational Background of Students.

The relation across dropout rate with regard to Schooling Background and Origin of Students and Educational Background are discussed here.

a1) *Dropout rate across origin of students and schooling background*

It was found (Table-5.8) that 61.8 percent of respondents among total respondents in ≤ 5 percent dropout category, opined that 'government schooling background' have majority in dropout. It resembles to results as of overall dropout. But results show contradiction in 6-10 percent dropout category and 16-10 percent dropout category. The lack of awareness about the opportunities available in tourism industry among government schools can be a reason for their dropout.

Table 5.8: Dropout rate and origin/schooling background

Dropout rate (%)	Origin of students			Schooling Background			
	Other State	Same State(s)	Total	Private	Government	Correspondence	Total
≤ 5	35 39.3% 77.8%	54 60.7% 64.3%	89 100.0% 69.0%	30 33.7% 58.8%	55 61.8% 75.3%	4 4.5% 80.0%	89 100.0% 69.0%
6-10	8 36.4% 17.8%	14 63.6% 16.7%	22 100.0% 17.1%	12 54.5% 23.5%	9 40.9% 12.3%	1 4.5% 20.0%	22 100.0% 17.1%
11-15	1 14.3% 2.2%	6 85.7% 7.1%	7 100.0% 5.4%	3 42.9% 5.9%	4 57.1% 5.5%	0 0.0% 0.0%	7 100.0% 5.4%
16-20	1 11.1% 2.2%	8 88.9% 9.5%	9 100.0% 7.0%	5 55.6% 9.8%	4 44.4% 5.5%	0 0.0% 0.0%	9 100.0% 7.0%
>20	0 0.0% 0.0%	2 100.0% 2.4%	2 100.0% 1.6%	1 50.0% 2.0%	1 50.0% 1.4%	0 0.0% 0.0%	2 100.0% 1.6%
Total	45 34.9% 100.0%	84 65.1% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%	51 39.5% 100.0%	73 56.6% 100.0%	5 3.9% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

It was found that 69.0 percent of academicians mentioned that majority of dropout rate is ≤ 5 percent. Among this percentage i.e. 69.0 as total, 60.7 percent academicians opined that majority of the drop out students, are from same States. The

majority (65.1 percent) of academicians, have opinion that dropout rate as total of all categories was higher among *same State* students.

a2) Dropout rate and Educational Background of students

The table 5.9 expresses the information on relation dropout rate and Educational Background of students pursuing tourism programs. The students have Arts discipline as their educational backgrounds have highest dropout rate in all the dropout categories, except Commerce discipline. It is also found that respondents have majority for Arts discipline in overall. It reveals that students from tourism education background have very positive attitude to continue the tourism programme. Hence, applicants with educational background from tourism programmes are more interested to continue the study.

Table 5.9: Educational Background

Dropout rate (%)	Arts	Commerce	Science	Management	Only Tourism Background	Total
≤5	38 42.7% 63.3%	22 24.7% 71.0%	14 15.7% 87.5%	14 15.7% 82.4%	1 1.1% 20.0%	89 100.0% 69.0%
6-10	13 59.1% 21.7%	3 13.6% 9.7%	2 9.1% 12.5%	1 4.5% 5.9%	3 13.6% 60.0%	22 100.0% 17.1%
11-15	2 28.6% 3.3%	4 57.1% 12.9%	0 0.0% 0.0%	1 14.3% 5.9%	0 0.0% 0.0%	7 100.0% 5.4%
16-20	5 55.6% 8.3%	2 22.2% 6.5%	0 0.0% 0.0%	1 11.1% 5.9%	1 11.1% 20.0%	9 100.0% 7.0%
>20	2 100.0% 3.3%	0 0.0% 0.0%	0 0.0% 0.0%	0 0.0% 0.0%	0 0.0% 0.0%	2 100.0% 1.6%
Total	60 46.5% 100.0%	31 24.0% 100.0%	16 12.4% 100.0%	17 13.2% 100.0%	5 3.9% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

5.6 Opinion about Course Curriculum Development for Tourism Programs

It analyses about the inputs taken into consideration by academicians to; and tourism professionals’ opinion about stakeholders to; develop or design the

curriculum for tourism education programs at the Institution/Department. It investigates that 62.0 percent of academicians have opinions that for course curriculum development, inputs come from ‘Internal Faculty’, ‘Faculty members of other Universities’ and ‘Industry Professionals’. The 89.1 percent of tourism professionals have opinion that this existing network is best among other for course curriculum development.

Table 5.10: Designing of Course curriculum

Respondents	Inputs for course curriculum development				
	A	B	C	D	Total
Tourism Academicians	20.9	13.2	62.0	3.9	100.0
Tourism Professionals	5.4	5.4	89.1	--	100.0

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

A-Internal Faculty Only, B- Internal Faculty + Faculty members of other Universities, C- Internal Faculty + Faculty members of other Universities + Industry Professionals, D- Affiliated University.

5.6.1 Most desired approach for curriculum development

The opinions of tourism professionals and academicians about change in course curriculum development are discussed here. (N1-Government + Tourism Education Institute, N2-Government + Tourism Education Institute + Tourism Industry, N3-Government + Tourism Education Institute + Tourism Industry+ Tourism Board).

a) Academic approach for course curriculum design

Table 5.11 expresses the opinion of the tourism academicians about the level of benefits of mentioned networking for tourism education curriculum development. It can be articulated that academicians have accepted that N3 can be a best approach to replace the existing approach of course curriculum development. There is essential need to develop a network 3 (Government + Tourism Education Institute + Tourism Industry + Tourism Board) to make tourism education more beneficial for the community and society and travel industry. Table shows that among different networking, N3 is found most desirable among 65.9 percent of academicians for course curriculum development.

Table 5.11: Most desired approach by academicians.

Extent of benefit of networking	N1	N2	N3
	F (%)	F (%)	f(%)
Very Low	5 (3.9)	1 (.8)	3 (2.3)
Low	10 (7.8)	8 (6.2)	2 (1.6)
Moderate	46 (35.7)	24 (18.6)	13 (10.1)
High	33 (25.6)	52 (40.3)	26 (20.2)
Very High	35 (27.1)	44 (34.1)	85 (65.9)
Total	129 (100.0)	129 (100.0)	129(100.0)

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.
F-frequency of respondents.

b) Industrial approach for course curriculum design

Through table 5.12 it can be analysed that N3 (Government + Tourism Education Institute + Tourism Industry+ Tourism Board) is most desired approach among tourism professionals for course curriculum development. The 58.9 percent tourism professionals opined that N3 is key (*very high*) player for the benefits of tourism education. It can be concluded that there is immediate need to change the approach for course curriculum development.

Table 5.12: Most desired approach by industry professionals

Extent of benefit of networking	N1	N2	N3
	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)
Very Low	7 (5.4)	3 (2.3)	3 (2.3)
Low	26 (20.2)	14 (10.9)	8 (6.2)
Moderate	54 (41.9)	30 (23.3)	22 (17.1)
High	28 (21.7)	49 (38.0)	20 (15.5)
Very High	14 (10.9)	33 (25.60)	76 (58.9)
Total	129 (100.0)	129 (100.0)	129 (100.0)

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.
F-frequency of respondents.

5.7 Opinion on Tourism Education

5.7.1 Tourism professionals

There is a set of must require skills in tourism industry.

A) Must require skills from tourism graduates at respective travel-trade organization (Tourism professionals)

*() shows the no. of respondents.

The descending order of must require skills in travel companies are; Communication skills which include language and email handling (93.03%), Destination Knowledge (84.50%), Digital Skills (82.17%), MS Excel (72.87), Power Point Presentation (49.61%) and Specified field of interest of employees (47.29%).

Image 5.5: Must require skills?

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

*PPT- Power Point Presentation, LE- language and email.

*largest size of words depict the largest percentage/frequency

B) How do tourism professionals contribute to tourism education?

*() shows the no. of respondents.

It is found that tourism professionals participate in tourism education through Corporate Social Responsibility (47.29%), Tourism Education Promotion (41.09%), National Image Building (31.78%), Guest Lecturer (30.23%), Student Evaluation (17.05%) and Syllabus Update (16.27%). It concludes that tourism professionals are distancing from 'syllabus update' and 'students evaluation' practices and need to build a strong academia-industry interaction. It will definitely help to make narrow down the gap between requisite human resources demanded and produced human resources.

Image 5.6: Participation

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.
 *largest size of words depict the largest percentage/frequency

C) Subject specific knowledge required in travel organization (tourism professionals)

It talks about the opinion of tourism professionals regarding the “subject specific knowledge” required in tourism organisations in the country. It was tried to investigate that, to what extent tourism specific knowledge of below mentioned areas is required in travel trade organisation in India i.e. it reveals the demand for the particular subject in tourism organization. The opinions of tourism professionals about the rating of subject specific knowledge requirements are tabled with regard to, Airlines and Cargo Management (ACM), Travel Agent and Tour Operation (TATO), Tourism Law (TL), Tourism Software (TS), Accommodation (ACOM), Event Management (EM), Outdoor Activities (OA), Foreign Language (FL), On the Job Training (OJT), Destination Management (DM), Tourism Research (TR), Tourism Policy (TP) and Management Information System (MIS). It was also analysed the top five subject of importance in tourism industry through the opinions of tourism professionals. Although it was also found that ‘subject specific knowledge’ demanded varies from company to companies.

With regards to above mentioned areas: Table-5.13 expresses that the majority of respondents agreed upon the ‘*very high*’ demanded of subject specific knowledge in tourism industry except ‘foreign languages’ based knowledge and it has ‘*moderate*’ requirement.

Table 5.13: Specific subject knowledge

Level of	ACM	TATO	TL	TS	ACOM	EM	OA	FL	OJT	DM	TR	TP	MIS
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Skills Required	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%
Very Low	17.8	12.4	15.5	11.6	11.6	14.0	13.2	24.0	14.7	11.6	12.4	14.7	10.9
Low	22.5	17.1	19.4	20.9	16.3	14.0	16.3	14.7	14.0	13.2	20.2	16.3	18.6
Moderate	24.0	14.0	20.2	17.8	13.2	18.6	20.2	31.8	19.4	16.3	24.8	19.4	15.5
High	10.1	19.4	20.2	20.9	14.7	18.6	22.5	17.8	25.6	20.9	16.3	20.2	21.7
Very High	25.6	37.2	24.8	28.7	44.2	34.9	27.9	11.6	26.4	38.0	26.4	29.5	33.3
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

*Bold number shows the majority of respondents.

D) Ranking of tourism specified subject knowledge requirement in industry (Tourism professionals)

It is evident from table 5.14, that knowledge regarding *Accommodation* is top requirement followed by *Destination Management* based knowledge, and *Travel Agency and Tour Operation* based expertise is third most desired field in tourism trade. Although, the *Management Information System* is fourth and *Event Management* is fifth most priority based subject specific knowledge desired in tourism industry. The top five 'subject specific knowledge requirement is in tourism industry over another explained as:

d1) With regard to accommodation, the pricing, target market, quality of services and satisfaction of clientele by the accommodation industry led to brand loyalty and favourable word-of-mouth promotion (Tsai et al. 2009). A research has shown that one third of tour expenditure goes to avail accommodation (Sharpley, 2000).

d2) Destination Management: Professionalism in destination management helps to understand the demand of clientele and to diversify the tourism product and influence the tourism industry development. Expertise in concerned subject can lead to enhance the pleasure of clientele also (Batinic, 2018).

d3) With regard to knowledge regarding Travel Agency and Tour Operation, it is foundation to run the tourism industry.

d4) The era of 'travel, tourism and technology' has led to the importance of Management Information System (Amoako et al. 2015).

d5) Event Management: Events are an important entity of societies and tourism across the globe. Events play an important role to attract tourists to a destination, and

its success depends upon the ability of human resource to utilise management skills (Oklobdzija, 2015).

Table 5.14: Ranking of tourism specified subject knowledge

Specific Subject	Mean	SD	Ranking
Accommodation	3.64	1.47	1
Destination Management	3.60	1.41	2
Travel Agent and Tour Operation	3.52	1.45	3
Management Information System	3.48	1.40	4
Event Management	3.47	1.44	5
Outdoor Activities	3.36	1.39	6
On the Job Training	3.35	1.39	7
Tourism Software/Application	3.34	1.39	8
Tourism Policy	3.33	1.43	9
Tourism Research	3.24	1.37	10
Tourism Law	3.19	1.41	11
Airlines and Cargo Management	3.03	1.44	12
Foreign Language	2.78	1.31	13

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

E) Level of Skills incorporated and skills found among tourism graduates

These are the skills which are measured through the opinions of academicians and industry professionals: Confidence Level (CL), Foreign Language (FL), Communication Skills (Com S), Travel Software (TS), Outdoor skills (OS), Research Skills (RS), Presentation Skills (PS), Digital Skills (DS), Sales Skills (SS), Marketing Skills (MS), Travel Ethics Skills (TES) and Tourism Industry Ethics (TIES). It is discussed here about the level of skills incorporated in tourism graduates at the completion of programs and level of skills found by tourism professionals at the time of hiring. Tourism academicians and tourism professionals have common opinion that the level of *Research Skills* and *Digital Skills* are *moderate* among tourism graduates while *Presentation Skills* and *Marketing Skills* are of *high* level. Majority of tourism professionals have a feeling that *Foreign Language Skills* and *Tourism Software Skills* are *very poor* although tourism academicians leveled same skills as *moderate* among tourism graduates. None of the skills was incorporated at *very high* level in the opinion of tourism academicians, although tourism

professionals found that ‘Sales Skills’ and ‘Presentation Skills’ are of ‘very high’ category among tourism graduates at the time of hiring.

Table 5.15: Opinion about skill level

Skills	Opinion of Academicians					Opinion of Industry Professionals				
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High
CL	3.1	9.3	25.6	42.6	19.4	5.4	10.1	23.3	28.7	32.6
FLS	15.5	25.6	34.1	14.0	10.9	34.9	24.8	18.6	13.2	8.5
CS	2.3	10.9	34.9	43.4	8.5	3.1	11.6	24.0	31.0	30.2
TS	13.2	19.4	38.8	12.4	16.3	24.0	21.7	33.3	14.7	6.2
OS	5.4	9.3	29.5	29.5	26.4	10.9	18.6	45.7	17.8	7.0
RS	13.2	20.2	38.8	17.1	10.9	17.8	30.2	32.6	17.1	2.3
PS	3.1	12.4	20.9	47.3	16.3	7.0	13.2	31.8	33.3	14.7
DS	3.9	14.7	35.7	28.7	17.7	14.0	26.4	29.5	18.6	11.6
SS	3.1	20.2	29.5	31.8	15.5	11.6	13.2	23.3	22.5	29.5
MS	3.1	18.6	29.5	34.9	14.0	12.2	14.0	26.4	27.9	19.4
TES	4.7	15.5	28.7	27.1	24.0	7.0	12.4	24.0	29.5	27.1
TIES	3.9	14.0	26.4	31.8	24.0	9.3	14.0	27.9	25.6	23.3

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

F) Rating of skills incorporated (by Tourism Academicians) and skills found (by Tourism Professionals)

Table 5.16 shows the opinions of academicians on a set of skills which are incorporated in tourism graduates at the completion of course, and rating of same set of skills found in tourism graduates at the time of hiring.

The tourism professionals opined that at the time of hiring, it was found among tourism graduates that *Outdoor skills, Digital Skills, Travel Software Skills, Research Skills and Foreign Language Skills* are incorporated below *moderate* (2.91-2.36) by tourism academicians. It is contradictory as tourism academicians rated *Outdoor Skills and Digital Skills*, incorporated ‘*above moderate*’ (3.62-3.40) category. It was found that among the below mentioned 12 skills, none of the skills was incorporated *excellently*. The opinion of academicians and tourism professionals rated *Communication Skills, Confidence Level, Travel Ethics Skills, Sales Skills, Travel Industry Ethics Skills (TIES), Presentation Skills and Marketing Skills* as ‘*above moderate*’. It shows there is room to improve these skills and give rise to effective and efficient networking among the tourism industry stakeholders i.e.

academicians, industry professionals, policy makers and State/Centre tourism corporations.

Table 5.16: Rating of basic skills

Tourism Professionals			Tourism Academicians		
Skills	Mean	S.D.	Skills	Mean	S.D.
Communication Skills	3.74	1.11	Confidence Level	3.66	1.00
Confidence Level	3.73	1.18	Outdoor skills	3.62	1.13
Travel Ethics Skills	3.57	1.21	Presentation Skills	3.61	1.00
Sales Skills	3.45	1.35	TIES	3.58	1.12
TIES	3.40	1.25	Travel Ethics Skills	3.50	1.15
Presentation Skills	3.36	1.10	Communication Skills	3.45	0.88
Marketing Skills	3.28	1.27	Digital Skills	3.40	1.06
Outdoor skills	2.91	1.04	Marketing Skills	3.38	1.04
Digital Skills	2.88	1.21	Sales Skills	3.36	1.07
Travel Software skills	2.57	1.18	Travel Software skills	2.99	1.23
Research Skills	2.56	1.05	Research Skills	2.92	1.16
Foreign Language	2.36	1.31	Foreign Language	2.79	1.19

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Chart 5.8 depicts that Confidence Level, Communication Skills, Sales Skills, and Travel Ethics Skills are found above the expectations of employer i.e. ‘skills incorporated’ are above ‘skills found’ by tourism employers. In addition, Foreign Language Skills, Tourism Software, Outdoor Skills, Research skills, Presentation skills, Digital skills, Marketing Skills and Tourism Industry Ethics (TIES) are below the expectations as per the respondents from tourism industry.

Chart 5.8: Skills rated by tourism professionals and tourism academicians

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

*Confidence Level (CL), Foreign Language (FL), Communication Skills (Com S), Travel Software (TS), Outdoor skills (OS), Research Skills (RS), Presentation Skills (PS), Digital Skills (DS), Sales Skills (SS), Marketing Skills (MS), Travel Ethics Skills (TES) , Tourism Industry Ethics (TIES)

G) Desired improvements in tourism curriculum being taught

The following table shows the opinion of Academicians and Industry Professionals, to what extent the below mentioned areas require improvement/changes for delivering an ideal tourism education. The Frequent syllabus Update (FSU), Industry Interaction (II), Job Training (JT), Research (Res.), Foreign Language (FL), Tourism Software (TS), Digital Skills (DS), Library Resources (LR), Academia-Industry Network (AIN) and Student Exchange Programs (SEP) are the areas of concern in this study. The tourism professionals have opinion to make a big improvement in all of the above mentioned areas except Library Resources and Foreign Languages. The majority of respondents either tourism academicians or industrial professionals have opinion that to deliver ideal tourism education/to produce ideal tourism professionals in the country very high need of improvement/changes and incorporation of Industry-Interaction, Job Training, Academia-Industry Network and Student Exchange Programs.

Table 5.17: Opinion on areas of improvement

Skills	Opinion of Industry Professionals					Opinion of Academicians				
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High
FSU	6.2	6.2	29.5	17.1	41.1	4.7	13.2	33.3	22.5	26.4
II	4.7	8.5	17.1	22.5	47.3	--	10.1	27.9	30.2	31.8
JT	3.1	6.2	21.7	32.6	36.4	3.1	12.4	17.8	31.8	34.9
Res.	7.0	10.9	23.3	29.5	29.5	1.6	7.8	34.1	35.7	20.9
FL	8.5	14.0	33.3	21.7	22.5	7.8	9.3	34.9	31.0	17.1
TS	7.0	11.6	25.6	27.9	27.9	7.0	10.1	26.4	30.2	26.4
DS	5.4	9.3	21.7	26.4	37.2	3.1	10.1	30.2	27.9	28.7
LR	7.0	18.6	37.2	20.9	16.3	1.6	9.3	25.6	40.3	23.3
AIN	4.7	10.9	25.6	27.9	31.0	2.3	5.4	29.5	22.5	40.3
SEP	7.0	7.8	27.1	24.0	34.1	7.0	10.9	20.9	20.9	40.3

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

H) Top domains desired for improvement

The tourism professionals have opinion that Industry Interaction ($\bar{x}=3.99$), Job Training ($\bar{x}=3.93$), Frequent Syllabus Updates/Digital Skills ($\bar{x}=3.81$), Student Exchange Programs ($\bar{x}=3.71$) and Academia Industry Network ($\bar{x}=3.70$) are the top five domains which need improvement to produce excellent tourism graduates. The findings also show that the priority domains for academicians are Academia Industry Network ($\bar{x}=3.93$), Industry Interaction ($\bar{x}=3.84$), Job Training ($\bar{x}=3.83$), Student Exchange Program ($\bar{x}=3.77$) and Library resources ($\bar{x}=3.74$). The data imply that tourism professionals asking for more changes in syllabus and more upgradation in digital skill among produced tourism graduates. The improvement in library resources is last priority among tourism professionals while tourism academicians placed it at fifth most priority for improvement.

Table 5.18: Ranking as per most desired improvement

Tourism Professionals			Tourism Academicians		
Skills	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Deviation	Skills	Mean(\bar{x})	Std. Deviation
Industry Interaction	3.99	1.19	Academia Industry Network	3.93	1.06
Job Training	3.93	1.05	Industry Interaction	3.84	.99
Frequent Syllabus Update	3.81	1.2	Job Training	3.83	1.13
Digital Skills in tourism	3.81	1.19	Student Exchange Program	3.77	1.28
Student Exchange Program	3.71	1.21	Library resources	3.74	.97
Academia Industry Network	3.70	1.18	Digital Skills in tourism	3.69	1.09
Research	3.64	1.21	Research	3.67	.95
Tourism software training	3.58	1.21	Tourism software training	3.59	1.18
Foreign Language	3.36	1.28	Frequent Syllabus Update	3.53	1.15
Library resources	3.21	1.14	Foreign Language	3.40	1.11

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Graph 5.4 shows that Research, Tourism Software Training and Foreign Language are the domains where tourism professionals and academicians have resemblance of opinions with regards to improvement and change in these skills.

Graph 5.3: Point of resemblance

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

I) Rating of Tourism Education in the country

Tourism education is exponentially growing in the country but it is failed to match the demand of industry. The perception of tourism academicians and industry professionals about the level of excellence is being measured here.

a) Academicians

Table 5.19 communicates the opinion of tourism academicians pertaining to the rating of current status of tourism education in the country. It was found that the majority (45.9 percent) of total academicians as well as individual percentage of designations (Professor- 46.7, Associate Professor- 43.8, Assistant Professor- 46.5, Guest Faculty- 43.8, Researchers-46.2) have an opinion that tourism education being provided in the country is '*moderate*'.

The status of tourism education can be improved in India through frequent syllabus update, digital skills development, AIN, Student exchange program, research skills and specialization based education).

Table 5.19: Rating of Tourism Education by Academicians

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across status of tourism education					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	0 0.0% 0.0%	2 13.3% 8.7%	7 46.7% 11.9%	4 26.7% 12.9%	2 13.3% 22.2%	15 100.0% 11.6%
Associate Professor	1 6.2% 14.3%	2 12.5% 8.7%	7 43.8% 11.9%	4 25.0% 12.9%	2 12.5% 22.2%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Assistant Professor	1 2.3% 14.3%	5 11.6% 21.7%	20 46.5% 33.9%	15 34.9% 48.4%	2 4.7% 22.2%	43 100.0% 33.3%
Guest Faculty	0 0.0% 0.0%	4 25.0% 17.4%	7 43.8% 11.9%	2 12.5% 6.5%	3 18.8% 33.3%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	5 12.8% 71.4%	10 25.6% 43.5%	18 46.2% 30.5%	6 15.4% 19.4%	0 0.0% 0.0%	39 100.0% 30.2%
Total	7 5.4% 100.0%	23 17.8% 100.0%	59 45.7% 100.0%	31 24.0% 100.0%	9 7.0% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

b) Industry professional

The majority (45.0 percent) of tourism professionals have rated current Indian tourism education system as '*moderate*'. There are 53.4 percent from Low Management and 51.4 percent from Top Management contributing towards the opinion of majority of tourism professionals. The Middle Management (26.5 percent) has placed tourism education in *low* category.

Table 5.20: Rating of Tourism Education by industry professionals

Level of management	Rating of Tourism Education in the country					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	7	6	31	8	6	58
	12.1%	10.3%	53.4%	13.8%	10.3%	100.0%
	38.9%	33.3%	53.4%	40.0%	40.0%	45.0%
Middle	3	9	8	8	6	34
	8.8%	26.5%	23.5%	23.5%	17.6%	100.0%
	16.7%	50.0%	13.8%	40.0%	40.0%	26.4%
Top	8	3	19	4	3	37
	21.6%	8.1%	51.4%	10.8%	8.1%	100.0%
	44.4%	16.7%	32.8%	20.0%	20.0%	28.7%
Total	18	18	58	20	15	129
	14.0%	14.0%	45.0%	15.5%	11.6%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

c) Academicians, Industry professionals and tourism education

It is clear from the table that country is practicing *moderate* tourism education. There is still an improvement required to cater the demand of tourism industry as well as need to nourish the potential of students.

Table 5.21: Respondents and Tourism Education

Respondents	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	Total
Professionals	18 (14.0)	18(14.0)	58 (45.0)	20 (15.4)	15 (11.6)	129 (100)
Academicians	7 (5.4)	23 (17.8)	59 (45.7)	31 (24.0)	9 (7.0)	129 (100)

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

D) Academicians and satisfaction with Tourism Education Syllabus

Chart reveals the satisfaction among tourism academicians about tourism education being imparted in respective institutions. The data proclaimed that 52.7 percent of academicians are satisfied with tourism education which is practiced in the respective department while 47.3 percent of academicians are on the other side of coin.

Chart 5.9: Academicians and Satisfaction with syllabus

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

E) Industry professionals and rating of Tourism professionals being produced in the country

Chart shows that only 13.4 percent of respondents opined that produced tourism professionals are excellent otherwise majority (67.4 percent) have placed that tourism professionals are moderately efficient to serve the tourism industry.

Chart 5.10: Rating of tourism professionals

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

F) Opinion on level of relevance of tourism education for the followings:

The opinion of industry professionals and academicians on relevance of tourism education to achieve Sustainable Development (SD), International Peace (IP), National Image Building (NIB), Economic Development (ED) and Environment Conservation (EC) are presented in table 5.22.

Table 5.22: Relevance of tourism education

Relevance of tourism education for	Industry Professionals (per cent)					Opinion of Academicians (Per cent)				
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High
SD	2 (1.6)	3 (2.3)	26 (20.2)	47 (36.4)	51 (39.5)	1 (0.8)	6 (4.7)	25 (19.4)	41 (31.8)	56 (43.4)
IP	8 (6.2)	10 (7.8)	43 (33.3)	38 (29.5)	30 (23.3)	2 (1.6)	-	41 (31.8)	47 (36.4)	39 (30.2)
NIB	4 (3.1)	3 (2.3)	30 (23.3)	46 (35.7)	46 (35.7)	1 (0.8)	4 (3.1)	17 (13.2)	49 (38.0)	58 (45.0)
ED	3 (2.3)	2 (1.6)	22 (17.1)	36 (27.9)	66 (51.2)	-	1 (0.8)	29 (22.5)	37 (28.7)	62 (48.1)
EC	3 (2.3)	2 (1.6)	28 (21.7)	35 (27.1)	61 (47.3)	1 (0.8)	6 (4.7)	34 (26.4)	30 (23.3)	58 (45.0)

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

***Bold** numbers represents the majority of respondents

f1) Sustainable Development (SD): In regard to relevance of tourism education for sustainable development, 39.5per cent industry professionals and 43.4 per cent academicians have the opinion that tourism education is *very highly* needed for sustainable development.

f2) National Image Building (NIB): A Majority of 45.0 per cent academicians believe that tourism education programs are *very highly* valuable and help in NIB, while 35.7 percent of respondents from tourism industry have opinion that it tourism education is either highly or very highly relevant for NIB.

f3) Economic Development (ED): Majority from both the groups i.e. 51.2 per cent industry professionals and 48.1 per cent academicians believe that tourism education is *very highly* valuable for economic development. The results suggest that there is a major room for improvement and investment in human resource (tourism) capital, to tap the tourism potential for economic

development of the country. The higher education and training enables human resource towards increased output and led to economic development (Radcliffe, 2019).

f4) Environment Conservation (EC): Both category of respondents i.e. academicians (45.0 percent) and tourism industry professionals (47.3 percent) have the opinion that tourism education is *highly* necessary for environment conservation, as tourism education talks about the importance of environment for tourism and inculcates respect for environment among produced human resources.

G) Ranking with regards to relevance of area

Table 23 shows the ranking of ‘relevance of tourism education’ for various aspects of sustainable development, asserted though ‘mean of opinions’ of tourism academicians and industry professionals. Table-23 shows that, both the respondents i.e. tourism academicians and tourism professionals opined that tourism education is very highly relevant for ‘Economic Development’. The ‘Sustainable Development’ is third most priority for both the parties whereas ‘International Peace’ is ranked 5th to achieve through tourism education.

Table 5.23: Rating of opinion regarding relevance of tourism education

Ranking	Tourism Professionals			Tourism Academicians		
	Areas	Mean	SD	Areas	Mean	SD
1	ED	4.24	.95	ED	4.24	.83
2	EC	4.16	.97	NIB	4.23	.85
3	SD	4.10	.91	SD	4.12	.94
4	NIB	3.98	.98	EC	4.07	.99
5	IP	3.56	1.12	1P	3.94	.87

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

H) Opinion about Indian Tourism Services (ITS)

As National Committee on Tourism was formed in 1986 under the chairmanship of Mohammed Yunus and committee recommended the ‘reorganising’ the tourism department. The incorporation of ITS can be a step towards ‘reorganising’

the tourism department. It will provide myriad opportunities to tourism graduates and consequently effective and efficient human resources for visionary planning about tourism. The table 5.24 expresses that majority of academicians (91.47 percent) as well as tourism professionals (88.47 percent) feel the need of incorporation of Indian Tourism Services for tourism graduates to explore the unrealised capability of tourism for societal expansion and sustainability unlike ‘general administrator’. Sofique (2013) has also advocated the need for ITS because tourism is highly relevant for employment generation, economic growth, infrastructure development, socio-cultural understanding, peace, ecological and many more.

Table 5.24: Indian Tourism Service

Respondents	No	Yes	Total
Tourism Professionals	15 (11.63)	114 (88.37)	129 (100)
Academicians	11 (8.53)	118 (91.47)	129 (100)

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

5.8 Crosstab Analysis of Satisfaction with Tourism Education Syllabus

In this part of the study, the crosstab analysis is conducted across ‘satisfaction with tourism education syllabus’ and with respect to different variable i.e. years of teaching, status of tourism education in the country, relevance of tourism education for International Peace, Sustainable Development, National Image Building, Economic Development, Environment Conservation and Product Development.

A) Years of teaching and satisfaction with Tourism Education Syllabus

The distribution between years of teaching as tourism academician and satisfaction with Tourism Education Syllabus being taught in institution is presented in table 5.25. Among academicians with teaching years more than 20 years, it was found 78.57 per cent are satisfied with current tourism curriculum in institution. But 52.85 percent respondents with teaching year ≤ 5 are not satisfied with existing departmental tourism curriculum. Total numbers of academicians in tourism are not satisfied with tourism education syllabus, among them 60.7 percent have teaching experience ≤ 5 years.

Table 5.25: Satisfaction and years of teaching

Years of teaching as Tourism Academician	Satisfaction with Tourism Education Syllabus		Total
	No	Yes	
≤5	37 52.85% 60.7%	33 47.1% 48.5%	70 100.0% 54.3%
6-10	10 52.6% 16.4%	9 47.4% 13.2%	19 100.0% 14.7%
11-15	4 28.6% 6.6%	10 71.4% 14.7%	14 100.0% 10.9%
16-20	7 58.3% 11.5%	5 41.7% 7.4%	12 100.0% 9.3%
>20	3 21.4% 4.9%	11 78.57% 16.2%	14 100.0% 10.9%
Total	61 47.3% 100.0%	68 52.7% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

It is clear from the chart-5.5 that ‘years of teaching’ lead to satisfaction about curriculum being taught in the department. The highest percentage of difference between ‘satisfied’ and ‘not-satisfied’ with tourism education syllabus is highest among those academicians who have teaching experience more than 20 years. Hence there is need for ‘re-skilling’ and ‘de-jobbing’ approach among senior academicians.

Graph 5.4: Satisfaction/year of teaching

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

*A-≤5 years, B-6-10 years, C-11-15 years, D-16-20 years, E->20 years.

B) Crosstab analysis of opinions of academicians regarding tourism education and Indian Tourism Services

Table 5.26 puts forward the opinion of tourism academicians about, the incorporation of Indian Tourism Services for tourism graduates can be one of the reasons for image building of tourism education and tourism promotion in the country. There are 88.5 percent academicians from ‘not satisfied’ category and 94.1 percent from ‘satisfied category’ in favor of incorporation of ITS. The majority of academicians from both the categories i.e. satisfied or not satisfied with tourism education syllabus being delivered in the country, are in favor of incorporation of Indian Tourism Services in the country. The National Committee on Tourism (1987) and Sofique (2013) have talked about ‘reorganisation’ of tourism departments and incorporation of ITS respectively.

Table 5.26: Satisfaction and ITS

Satisfaction with Tourism Education Syllabus	Indian Tourism Services (ITS)		Percent
	No	Yes	
No	7 (11.5%)	54 (88.5%)	61 (100%)
Yes	04 (5.9%)	64 (94.1%)	68 (100%)

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

The majority were found in favour of incorporation of ITS come from satisfied tourism academicians.

C) Opinion about Academic satisfaction and status of tourism education

Table 5.27 shows association between satisfaction with ‘tourism education syllabus’ in the institution and ‘status of tourism education in the country’. It is found that tourism academicians either satisfied or not satisfied have opined that status of tourism education is *moderate*.

Table 5.27: Satisfaction and status of tourism education

Satisfaction with Tourism Education Syllabus	Status of Tourism Education					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
No	6	14	27	10	4	61
	9.8%	23.0%	44.3%	16.4%	6.6%	100.0%
Yes	1	9	32	21	5	68
	1.5%	13.2%	47.1%	30.9%	7.4%	100.0%
	14.3%	39.1%	54.2%	67.7%	55.6%	52.7%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: Tourism education in the country is *moderate*. In *moderate* category, the majority (54.2 percent) reside in ‘satisfied’ academicians.

D) Tourism education Satisfaction and International Peace

The table 5.28 indicates that among the total respondents, 47.3 percent are ‘not satisfied’ with current tourism education; within these respondents 39.3 percent feels that tourism education is highly relevant to bring International Peace. The 52.7 percent of total academicians are ‘satisfied’ with tourism education and 35.3 percent of its sub-respondents feel that it is *moderately* responsible toward International Peace.

Tables 5.28: Tourism education and International Peace

Satisfaction with Tourism Education Syllabus	International Peace				Total
	Very Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
No	1	17	24	19	61
	1.6%	27.9%	39.3%	31.1%	100%
Yes	1	24	23	20	68
	1.5%	35.3%	33.8%	29.4%	100%
	50.0%	58.5%	48.9%	51.3%	52.7%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

E) Tourism education Satisfaction and National Image Building

Table 5.29 accentuates the distribution between the satisfaction of tourism academicians with the tourism education being imparted and their views about National Image Building. The table shows that there are 52.7 percent respondents

consider the present tourism education *very satisfactory*. But among *satisfied respondents* only 45.6 percent respondents agree with the fact that the tourism education is *very highly* relevant to the Nation Image Building.

Table 5.29: Tourism education and National Image Building

Satisfaction with Tourism Education Syllabus	National Image Building					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
No	0	3	7	24	27	61
	0	4.9%	11.5%	39.3%	44.3%	100%
	0	75.0%	41.2%	49.0%	46.6%	47.3%
Yes	1	1	10	25	31	68
	1.5%	1.5%	14.7%	36.8%	45.6%	100%
	100.0%	25.0%	58.8%	51.0%	53.4%	52.7%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

F) Tourism education Satisfaction and Sustainable Development

The data accentuate that among the satisfied respondents, 45.6 percent opined that tourism education is *highly* relevant for Sustainable Development. The majority (41.0 percent) of respondents from ‘not satisfied’ category opined that it is *very highly* relevant for sustainable development. It concludes that academicians feel the importance for a wider goal of Sustainable Development either they are satisfied or not with current curriculum practices.

Table 5.30: Tourism education and Sustainable Development

Satisfaction with Tourism Education Syllabus	Sustainable Development					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
No	0	4	11	21	25	61
	0	6.6%	18.0%	34.4%	41.0%	100%
	0	66.7%	44.0%	51.2%	44.6%	47.3%
Yes	1	2	14	20	31	68
	1.5%	2.9%	20.6%	29.4%	45.6%	100%
	100.0%	33.3%	56.0%	48.8%	55.4%	52.7%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

G) Tourism education Satisfaction and Economic Development

Irrespective of satisfaction opinion, majority of academicians feel that tourism education is *very highly* relevant to Economic Development.

Table 5.31: Tourism education and Economic Development

Satisfaction with Tourism Education Syllabus	Economic Development				Total
	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
No	1	11	20	29	61
	1.6%	18.0%	32.8%	47.5%	100%
	100.0%	37.9%	54.1%	46.8%	47.3%
Yes	0	18	17	33	68
	0	26.5%	25.0%	48.5%	100%
	0	62.1%	45.9%	53.2%	52.7%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

H) Tourism education Satisfaction and Environment Conservation

Results show that tourism academicians have understanding that tourism education is helpful for Environment Conservation. Irrespective of satisfaction opinion, majority of academicians have a feeling that tourism education is *very highly* relevant to Environment Conservation.

Table 5.32: Tourism Education and Environment Conservation

Satisfaction with Tourism Education Syllabus	Environment Conservation					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
No	0	1	12	20	28	61
	0	1.6%	19.7%	32.8%	45.9%	100%
	0	16.7%	35.3%	66.7%	48.3%	47.3%
Yes	1	5	22	10	30	68
	1.5%	7.4%	32.4%	14.7%	44.1%	100%
	100.0%	83.3%	64.7%	33.3%	51.7%	52.7%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

I) Tourism education Satisfaction and Product Development

Irrespective of satisfaction opinion, majority of academicians consider that tourism education is *very highly* relevant to Product Development.

Table 5.33: Tourism education and product development

Satisfaction with Tourism Education Syllabus	Product Development					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
No	0	0	13	21	27	61
	0	0	21.3%	34.4%	44.3%	100%
	0	0	44.8%	48.8%	50.0%	47.3%
Yes	1	2	16	22	27	68
	1.5%	2.9%	23.5%	32.4%	39.7%	100%
	100.0%	100.0%	55.2%	51.2%	50.0%	52.7%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key findings: The analysis of tables (5.28 to 5.23) reveals that the majority of academicians ‘not-satisfied’ with tourism education being imparted in the department/institution have opinion that tourism education is highly relevant to International Peace and *very highly* relevant to Product Development and Environment Conservation. Those academicians who are ‘satisfied’ with tourism education infused among tourism graduates, have opinion that tourism education is *very highly* relevant to National Image Building, Economic Development and Sustainable Development.

5.9 Crosstab analysis with regards to status of tourism education in India

A) Distribution of opinion across teaching years and status of tourism education

Irrespective of teaching of years as academicians (except 16-20 years), majority (45.7 percent) of the academicians have mentioned that ‘status of tourism education’ in the country is *moderate*.

Table 5.34: Years of teaching and status of tourism education

Years of teaching as Tourism Academician	Status of Tourism Education					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
≤5	4	15	33	15	3	70
	5.7%	21.4%	47.1%	21.4%	4.3%	100.0%
	57.1%	65.2%	55.9%	48.4%	33.3%	54.3%
6-10	2	4	8	4	1	19
	10.5%	21.1%	42.1%	21.1%	5.3%	100.0%
	28.6%	17.4%	13.6%	12.9%	11.1%	14.7%
11-15	0	1	9	4	0	14
	0.0%	7.1%	64.3%	28.6%	0.0%	100.0%
	0.0%	4.3%	15.3%	12.9%	0.0%	10.9%
16-20	0	1	4	5	2	12
	0.0%	8.3%	33.3%	41.7%	16.7%	100.0%
	0.0%	4.3%	6.8%	16.1%	22.2%	9.3%
>20	1	2	5	3	3	14
	7.1%	14.3%	35.7%	21.4%	21.4%	100.0%
	14.3%	8.7%	8.5%	9.7%	33.3%	10.9%
Total	7	23	59	31	9	129
	5.4%	17.8%	45.7%	24.0%	7.0%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: In *moderate* category majority (55.9 percent) resides in those academicians having teaching experience ≤ 5 years.

B) The frequency distribution among status of tourism education and tourism professionals

Table 5.35 shows the opinion of tourism professionals across ‘rating of tourism education’ in the country by industry professionals and ‘tourism professionals being produced’ by tourism education.

The majority (45.0 percent) of respondents from tourism industry rated that tourism education in the country is *moderate*. In this rating, the majority (79.3 percent) rated that tourism professionals being produced in the country are neither excellent nor poor in professionalism i.e. they are *moderate*.

Table 5.35: Tourism education and tourism professionals

Rating of Tourism Education	Rating of Tourism Professionals			Total
	Poor	Moderate	Excellent	
Very low	7	10	1	18
	38.9%	55.6%	5.6%	100%
	28.0%	11.5%	5.9%	14.0%
Low	3	15	0	18
	16.7 %	83.3%	0	100
	12%	17.2 %	0	14%
Moderate	8	46	4	58
	13.8%	79.3%	6.9%	100
	32%	52.9%	23.5%	45%
High	3	10	7	20
	15 %	50.0 %	35%	100
	12%	11.5%	41.2%	15.5%
Very High	4	6	5	15
	26.7%	40.0%	33.3%	100
	16%	6.9%	29.4%	11.6%
Total	25	87	17	129
	19.4%	67.4%	13.2%	100
	(100)	(100)	(100)	100

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: Those who rated tourism education as of *very high* quality in the country, among them the majority mentioned produced tourism professionals as *moderate*. However, those who responded that produced tourism professionals are

excellent, among them the majority feel tourism education is also not *excellent* (very high quality).

5.10 Analysis of specialisation, rating of tourism professionals and ITS

Here, it was analysed the opinion of tourism professionals with relation to specialisation and tourism professional rating; specialisation and ITS.

A) Tourism Professionals being produced by Tourism Education and specialization

Table 5.36 reveals the distribution of rating of ‘tourism professionals’ across any ‘specialized services offered’ by concerned tourism organization. Those tourism professionals offer ‘specialised services’ among them the majority (62.7 percent) rated tourism professionals as *moderate*.

Table 5.36: specialization and professionals’ rating

Rating of Tourism Professionals	Specialization		Total
	No	Yes	
Poor	2	23	25
	8.0%	92.0%	100.0%
	7.4%	22.5%	19.4%
Moderate	23	64	87
	26.4%	73.6%	100.0%
	85.2%	62.7%	67.4%
Excellent	2	15	17
	11.8%	88.2%	100.0%
	7.4%	14.7%	13.2%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: It reveals that produced professionals are not fully capable to cater the tourism industry and lack in specialised tourism education.

B) Specialisation and need for ITS for tourism graduates

It was discussed here about the relationship between specializations based travel organization respondents and the demand of Indian Tourism Services (ITS). The data show that the majority (89.23 percent) from ‘specialization based’ travel trade organisations, endorse the idea of the implementation of Indian Tourism Services for tourism graduates. The majority (85.19 percent) from ‘non-specialisaton’ based oragisations also support the idea.

Table 5.37: Specialisation and ITS

Any Specialization	ITS		Total
	No	Yes	
No	4 (14.16)	23 (85.19)	27 (100)
Yes	11 (10.78)	91 (89.23)	102 (100)
Total	15 (12.50)	114 (88.37)	129

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: It portrays that the majority of tourism professionals, either offer specialised services or not, feel the need of Indian Tourism Services for tourism graduates.

C) Management level of tourism professionals and ITS

The tourism professionals accept that incorporation of Indian Tourism Services (ITS) tourism graduates will promote the tourism education in the country consequently will promote tourism also. There are 81.1 percent tourism professional from Top Management, 88.2 percent from Middle Management and 93.1 percent from Lower Management are in favor of incorporation of ITS.

Table 5.38: Tourism professionals and ITS

Level of management	Indian Tourism Services (ITS)		Total
	No	Yes	
Low	4	54	58
	6.9%	93.1%	100.0%
	26.7%	47.4%	45.0%
Middle	4	30	34
	11.8%	88.2%	100.0%
	26.7%	26.3%	26.4%
Top	7	30	37
	18.9%	81.1%	100.0%
	46.7%	26.3%	28.7%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: Across all the levels of management i.e. Top, Middle and Low management, there is urgent demand for incorporation of ITS.

5.11 Preference for ‘Subject Specific Knowledge’ among Top, Middle and Low Levels of Management

It was discussed here about the preferences of ‘subject specific knowledge’ in tourism industry across the different levels of management i.e. Top Management, Middle Management and Low Management. It was tried to analyse that among different level of management, which one falls in majority in *very high* category.

A) Level of Management and Airlines and Cargo Management

There are 29.3 percent tourism professionals from Low Management have opinion that mentioned subject has *moderate* relevance in tourism industry. Although, 32.4 percent from Middle Management and 35.1 percent tourism professionals from top level management have opinion that Airlines and Cargo Management based subject specific knowledge is *very highly* important in tourism organisation.

Table 5.39: Level of management and of airlines and cargo management

Level of management	Rating of airlines and cargo management specific knowledge required in tourism organisation.					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	15 25.9% 65.2%	11 19.0% 37.9%	17 29.3% 54.8%	6 10.3% 46.2%	9 15.5% 27.3%	58 100.0% 45.0%
Middle	5 14.7% 21.7%	9 26.5% 31.0%	6 17.6% 19.4%	3 8.8% 23.1%	11 32.4% 33.3%	34 100.0% 26.4%
Top	3 8.1% 13.0%	9 24.3% 31.0%	8 21.6% 25.8%	4 10.8% 30.8%	13 35.1% 39.4%	37 100.0% 28.7%
Total	23 17.8% 100.0%	29 22.5% 100.0%	31 24.0% 100.0%	13 10.1% 100.0%	33 25.6% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: Across all levels of management, only Top Management has the majority in *very high* category, it means airlines and cargo management based skills and knowledge are *very highly* demanded in tourism industry according to Top Management.

B) Level of Management and Travel agency and tour operation

The importance of subject knowledge of Travel agency and tour operation plays an important role in tourism organisation. It can be inferred from table that 40.5 percent of respondents from top level management, 29.4 percent among middle management and 39.7 percent from low level management accepts that knowledge of travel agency and tour operation is *very highly* important for tourism organisation.

Table 5.40: Level of management and Travel agent and tour operation

Level of management	Rating of Travel agent and tour operator specific knowledge required in tourism organization					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	1	11	11	12	23	58
	1.7%	19.0%	19.0%	20.7%	39.7%	100.0%
	6.2%	50.0%	61.1%	48.0%	47.9%	45.0%
Middle	5	7	5	7	10	34
	14.7%	20.6%	14.7%	20.6%	29.4%	100.0%
	31.2%	31.8%	27.8%	28.0%	20.8%	26.4%
Top	10	4	2	6	15	37
	27.0%	10.8%	5.4%	16.2%	40.5%	100.0%
	62.5%	18.2%	11.1%	24.0%	31.2%	28.7%
Total	16	22	18	25	48	129
	12.4%	17.1%	14.0%	19.4%	37.2%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: All levels of management have shown majority in *very high* category.

C) Level of Management and Tourism Law

Tourism Law subject stands at 11th rank with mean 3.19, out of 13 essential subjects for tourism industry (Table 5.14). The majority of Middle level Management is bifurcated between 'moderate' and 'very high' category of importance.

Table 5.41: Level of management and Tourism law

Level of management	Rating of Tourism Law specific knowledge required in Tourism organization					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	8	10	17	9	14	58
	13.8%	17.2%	29.3%	15.5%	24.1%	100.0%
	40.0%	40.0%	65.4%	34.6%	43.8%	45.0%
Middle	6	10	4	4	10	34
	17.6%	29.4%	11.8%	11.8%	29.4%	100.0%
	30.0%	40.0%	15.4%	15.4%	31.2%	26.4%
Top	6	5	5	13	8	37
	16.2%	13.5%	13.5%	35.1%	21.6%	100.0%
	30.0%	20.0%	19.2%	50.0%	25.0%	28.7%
Total	20	25	26	26	32	129
	15.5%	19.4%	20.2%	20.2%	24.8%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: Within management level none of the majority has found Tourism Law knowledge as *very highly* important in tourism industry.

D) Level of Management and Tourism software/application

Tourism Software/application subject stands at 8th rank with mean 3.34, out of 13 essential subjects for tourism industry (Table-5.14). The respondents from different levels of management have opined that ‘tourism software/applications’ have *very high* role of importance in travel and tourism business except Middle Management.

Table 5.42: Level of management and Tourism Software/application

Level of management	Rating of Tourism Software/application specific knowledge required in tourism organization					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	5	11	11	13	18	58
	8.6%	19.0%	19.0%	22.4%	31.0%	100.0%
	33.3%	40.7%	47.8%	48.1%	48.6%	45.0%
Middle	2	11	4	8	9	34
	5.9%	32.4%	11.8%	23.5%	26.5%	100.0%
	13.3%	40.7%	17.4%	29.6%	24.3%	26.4%
Top	8	5	8	6	10	37
	21.6%	13.5%	21.6%	16.2%	27.0%	100.0%
	53.3%	18.5%	34.8%	22.2%	27.0%	28.7%
Total	15	27	23	27	37	129
	11.6%	20.9%	17.8%	20.9%	28.7%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: Tourism software and knowledge about its application is *very highly* needed in tourism industry among Top and Low management.

E) Level of Management and Accommodation Industry specified knowledge

Accommodation subject stands at 1st rank with mean 3.64, out of 13 essential subjects for tourism industry (Table 5.14). The majority with in different levels of management i.e. Top (45.9 percent) Middle (29.4 percent) and Low (51.7 percent) management have opined that ‘accommodation industry specific knowledge’ is keystone player in tourism industry.

Table 5.43: Level of management and Accommodation industry

Level of management	Rating of Accommodation specific knowledge required in tourism organization					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	5	9	9	5	30	58
	8.6%	15.5%	15.5%	8.6%	51.7%	100.0%
	33.3%	42.9%	52.9%	26.3%	52.6%	45.0%
Middle	4	9	6	5	10	34
	11.8%	26.5%	17.6%	14.7%	29.4%	100.0%
	26.7%	42.9%	35.3%	26.3%	17.5%	26.4%
Top	6	3	2	9	17	37
	16.2%	8.1%	5.4%	24.3%	45.9%	100.0%
	40.0%	14.3%	11.8%	47.4%	29.8%	28.7%
Total	15	21	17	19	57	129
	11.6%	16.3%	13.2%	14.7%	44.2%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: The respondents from all the level of management have opined that Accommodation specific knowledge has *very high* role of importance in travel and tourism business.

F) Level of Management and Event Management specified knowledge

The Event Management subject stands at 5th rank with mean 3.47, out of 13 essential subjects for tourism industry (Table 5.14). Event management is among the specialised services offered by travel industry as responded by tourism professionals. The respondents from all the level of management have opined that Event Management has *very high* role of importance in travel and tourism business.

Table 5.44: Level of management and Event Management

Level of management	Rating of Event Management specific knowledge required in tourism organization					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	7	11	10	8	22	58
	12.1%	19.0%	17.2%	13.8%	37.9%	100.0%
	38.9%	61.1%	41.7%	33.3%	48.9%	45.0%
Middle	5	3	9	6	11	34
	14.7%	8.8%	26.5%	17.6%	32.4%	100.0%
	27.8%	16.7%	37.5%	25.0%	24.4%	26.4%
Top	6	4	5	10	12	37
	16.2%	10.8%	13.5%	27.0%	32.4%	100.0%
	33.3%	22.2%	20.8%	41.7%	26.7%	28.7%
Total	18	18	24	24	45	129
	14.0%	14.0%	18.6%	18.6%	34.9%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: The expertise about Event Management is *very highly* needed in current tourism industry as per the opinions of ‘all levels of management’.

G) Level of Management and exposure to Outdoor activities

The Outdoor Activities specific knowledge stands at 6th rank with mean 3.36, out of 13 essential subjects for tourism industry (Table-5.14). The order of preference is in ‘very high’ category among level of management; Top Management (29.7) >Low Management (29.3)>Middle Management (23.5).

Table 5.45: Level of management and Outdoor activities knowledge

Level of management	Rating of Outdoor Activities specific knowledge required in tourism organization					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	5	10	13	13	17	58
	8.6%	17.2%	22.4%	22.4%	29.3%	100.0%
	29.4%	47.6%	50.0%	44.8%	47.2%	45.0%
Middle	5	6	6	9	8	34
	14.7%	17.6%	17.6%	26.5%	23.5%	100.0%
	29.4%	28.6%	23.1%	31.0%	22.2%	26.4%
Top	7	5	7	7	11	37
	18.9%	13.5%	18.9%	18.9%	29.7%	100.0%
	41.2%	23.8%	26.9%	24.1%	30.6%	28.7%
Total	17	21	26	29	36	129
	13.2%	16.3%	20.2%	22.5%	27.9%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: The Top Management and Low Management have a feeling that exposure to outdoor activities among the tourism professionals should be of pre-eminence level.

H) Level of Management and Foreign language knowledge

Foreign Language subject stands at 13th rank with mean 2.78, out of 13 essential subjects for tourism industry (Table 5.14). In Low Management majority of respondents i.e. 36.2 percent and 37.8 percent from Top Management revealed the *moderate* importance of foreign language in tourism industry.

Table 5.46: Level of management and foreign language knowledge

Level of management	Rating of Foreign Language specific knowledge required in tourism organization					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	17	5	21	10	5	58
	29.3%	8.6%	36.2%	17.2%	8.6%	100.0%
	54.8%	26.3%	51.2%	43.5%	33.3%	45.0%
Middle	6	10	6	8	4	34
	17.6%	29.4%	17.6%	23.5%	11.8%	100.0%
	19.4%	52.6%	14.6%	34.8%	26.7%	26.4%
Top	8	4	14	5	6	37
	21.6%	10.8%	37.8%	13.5%	16.2%	100.0%
	25.8%	21.1%	34.1%	21.7%	40.0%	28.7%
Total	31	19	41	23	15	129
	24.0%	14.7%	31.8%	17.8%	11.6%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: Foreign language based specific skills are not among the top ten priorities among any of the management level.

I) Level of Management and On the Job Training exposure/practice

On the Job Training practice stands at 7th rank with mean 3.35, out of 13 essential subjects for tourism industry (Table 5.12). In Low Management 29.3 per cent, in Middle Management 23.5 percent and in Top Level Management 29.7 percent have majority of responses in favour of very high, moderate and high requirement of On the Job Training experience in the concerned travel trade organisation.

Table 5.47: Level of management and On the Job Training practice

Level of management	Rating of On the Job Training specific knowledge required in tourism organization					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	9	6	11	15	17	58
	15.5%	10.3%	19.0%	25.9%	29.3%	100.0%
	47.4%	33.3%	44.0%	45.5%	50.0%	45.0%
Middle	4	7	8	7	8	34
	11.8%	20.6%	23.5%	20.6%	23.5%	100.0%
	21.1%	38.9%	32.0%	21.2%	23.5%	26.4%
Top	6	5	6	11	9	37
	16.2%	13.5%	16.2%	29.7%	24.3%	100.0%
	31.6%	27.8%	24.0%	33.3%	26.5%	28.7%
Total	19	18	25	33	34	129
	14.7%	14.0%	19.4%	25.6%	26.4%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: It is the only Low Management which recommends On the Job Training is *highly* needed in tourism industry.

J) Level of Management and Destination Management specified knowledge

The Destination Management subject stands at 2nd rank with mean 3.60, out of 13 essential subjects for tourism industry (Table 5.14). The importance of professionalism expertise in destination management subject in tourism world can be elicited by the fact that 39.7 percent in Low Management, 32.4 percent in Middle Management and 40.5 percent in Top level Management have opined that Destination Management is *very highly* important.

Table 5.48: Level of management and Destination Management

Level of management	Rating of Destination Management specific knowledge required in tourism organization					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	8	6	11	10	23	58
	13.8%	10.3%	19.0%	17.2%	39.7%	100.0%
	53.3%	35.3%	52.4%	37.0%	46.9%	45.0%
Middle	2	9	4	8	11	34
	5.9%	26.5%	11.8%	23.5%	32.4%	100.0%
	13.3%	52.9%	19.0%	29.6%	22.4%	26.4%
Top	5	2	6	9	15	37
	13.5%	5.4%	16.2%	24.3%	40.5%	100.0%
	33.3%	11.8%	28.6%	33.3%	30.6%	28.7%
Total	15	17	21	27	49	129
	11.6%	13.2%	16.3%	20.9%	38.0%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: Destination Management based subject knowledge is *very highly* demanded in tourism industry as per the opinion of respondents from all level of management.

K) Level of Management and Tourism research specified knowledge

Tourism research subject stands at 10th rank with mean 3.24, out of 13 essential subjects for tourism industry (Table 5.14). There are 25.9 percent from Low Level Management opined moderate importance and 29.7 percent from Top Level Management argues that Tourism Research has *very high* use in tourism industry and its knowledge requirement as well (Table-5.49).

Table 5.49: Level of management and Tourism Research

Level of management	Rating of Tourism Research specific knowledge required in tourism organization					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	9	11	15	9	14	58
	15.5% 56.2%	19.0% 42.3%	25.9% 46.9%	15.5% 42.9%	24.1% 41.2%	100.0% 45.0%
Middle	2	9	9	5	9	34
	5.9% 12.5%	26.5% 34.6%	26.5% 28.1%	14.7% 23.8%	26.5% 26.5%	100.0% 26.4%
Top	5	6	8	7	11	37
	13.5% 31.2%	16.2% 23.1%	21.6% 25.0%	18.9% 33.3%	29.7% 32.4%	100.0% 28.7%
Total	16	26	32	21	34	129
	12.4% 100.0%	20.2% 100.0%	24.8% 100.0%	16.3% 100.0%	26.4% 100.0%	100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: It was found that Tourism Research skills are priority among Top Management in tourism industry.

L) Level of Management and Tourism policy specified knowledge

Tourism policy subject stands at 9th rank with mean 3.33, out of 13 essential subjects for tourism industry (Table 5.14).It is displayed in table-5.50 that 32.4 percent tourism professionals from Top Level Management have marked Tourism Research as very highly important and 31 percent from Low Level Management as well as 23.5 percent from Middle Level Management.

Table 5.50: Level of management and Tourism policy

Level of management	Rating of Tourism Policy specific knowledge required in tourism organization					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	9	8	11	12	18	58
	15.5%	13.8%	19.0%	20.7%	31.0%	100.0%
	47.4%	38.1%	44.0%	46.2%	47.4%	45.0%
Middle	5	7	7	7	8	34
	14.7%	20.6%	20.6%	20.6%	23.5%	100.0%
	26.3%	33.3%	28.0%	26.9%	21.1%	26.4%
Top	5	6	7	7	12	37
	13.5%	16.2%	18.9%	18.9%	32.4%	100.0%
	26.3%	28.6%	28.0%	26.9%	31.6%	28.7%
Total	19	21	25	26	38	129
	14.7%	16.3%	19.4%	20.2%	29.5%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: Tourism policy is one of those subjects which attract the predominant interest of all level of management.

M) Level of Management and Management Information System

The majority of respondents in low level management (39.7 percent) and middle management (32.4 percent) have asserted that MIS is need of the hours and have very high importance in tourism industry.35.1 percent in top level management favour the Management Information System is highly important in travel trade. Management Information System subject stands at 4th rank with mean 3.48, out of 13 essential subjects for tourism industry (table 5.14).

Table 5.51: Level of management and Management Information System

Level of management	Rating of Management Information System specific knowledge required in tourism organization					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	5	12	8	10	23	58
	8.6%	20.7%	13.8%	17.2%	39.7%	100.0%
	35.7%	50.0%	40.0%	35.7%	53.5%	45.0%
Middle	5	6	7	5	11	34
	14.7%	17.6%	20.6%	14.7%	32.4%	100.0%
	35.7%	25.0%	35.0%	17.9%	25.6%	26.4%
Top	4	6	5	13	9	37
	10.8%	16.2%	13.5%	35.1%	24.3%	100.0%
	28.6%	25.0%	25.0%	46.4%	20.9%	28.7%
Total	14	24	20	28	43	129
	10.9%	18.6%	15.5%	21.7%	33.3%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: Low Management and Middle Management have recognised that MIS based knowledge has key role in tourism industry.

Over view: Travel Agency and Tour Operation, Accommodation, Event Management, Destination Management and Tourism policy based knowledge is predominant in tourism industry as per the opinions or respondents from Top, Middle and Low management in tourism organisations.

5.12 Crosstab Analysis of Skills Enhanced and Skills Found

This section of the study analyses the perception of academicians and tourism professionals about the level of ‘skills incorporated’ and ‘skills found’ among tourism graduates. The base of the question was –Nature of skills developed; to what level do you think the following skills of the students enhance after the completion of the course. The opinion of tourism academicians (designation wise) and tourism professionals (management level wise) about level of Confidence Level (CL), Foreign Language, Communication, Travel Software, Outdoor, Research, Presentation, Digital, Sales, Marketing, Travel Ethics and Tourism Industry Ethics Skills developed in tourism graduates after completion of course and level of skills found in tourism graduates at the time of hiring. It was focused to knowing about *majority* in *very high* category.

5.12.1 Academicians and Skills Incorporated

A) Academic Designation and level of confidence incorporated

It was found that majority of the percentage of respondents i.e. Professors (40.0), Assistant Professors (62.8) and Researchers (35.9) have incorporated Confidence up to a high extent. The Associate Professors (31.2) have a feeling that skill ingrained has *low* level, and *very highly* developed in the view of Guest Faculty (37.5). Among all the respondents 42.6 percent feel that confidence level incorporated among graduates have *high* level. The highest to lowest percentage of respondents’ designation associated with *high* category are: Assistant professor > Researcher > Professor > associate professor = Guest faculty.

Table 5.52: Academic designation and confidence level incorporated

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of level of confidence across designation of academicians					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	0 0.0% 0.0%	0 0.0% 0.0%	5 33.3% 15.2%	6 40.0% 10.9%	4 26.7% 16.0%	15 100.0% 11.6%
Associate Professor	1 6.2% 25.0%	5 31.2% 41.7%	4 25.0% 12.1%	4 25.0% 7.3%	2 12.5% 8.0%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Assistant Professor	1 2.3% 25.0%	3 7.0% 25.0%	7 16.3% 21.2%	27 62.8% 49.1%	5 11.6% 20.0%	43 100.0% 33.3%
Guest Faculty	1 6.2% 25.0%	1 6.2% 8.3%	4 25.0% 12.1%	4 25.0% 7.3%	6 37.5% 24.0%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	1 2.6% 25.0%	3 7.7% 25.0%	13 33.3% 39.4%	14 35.9% 25.5%	8 20.5% 32.0%	39 100.0% 30.2%
Total	4 3.1% 100.0%	12 9.3% 100.0%	33 25.6% 100.0%	55 42.6% 100.0%	25 19.4% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: The majority of guest faculty have opinion that confidence level skills are perfectly incorporated, where as other designations are disagree with confidence level skills.

B) Academic designation and foreign language skills

The question regarding foreign language was asked to know that either European or Asian language are being taught. Foreign language skills developed after completion of tourism program are placed *moderate* by academicians who are 34.1 percent.

The highest to lowest percentage of respondents associated with *moderate* category are: Assistant professor> Researcher>Professors/Associate professor> Guest faculty

It was found that majority of the percentage of respondents i.e. Professors (33.3) and Assistant Professors (53.5) opined that Foreign Language Skills are incorporated *moderately*. The Associate Professors (37.5) have a feeling that foreign language skills are ingrained highly. In the view of Guest Faculty (37.5) and

Researchers (41.0) opined that foreign language skills are poorly developed among tourism graduates.

Table 5.53: Academic designation and foreign language

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across Foreign language skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	2	2	5	3	3	15
	13.3%	13.3%	33.3%	20.0%	20.0%	100.0%
	10.0%	6.1%	11.4%	16.7%	21.4%	11.6%
Associate Professor	1	3	5	6	1	16
	6.2%	18.8%	31.2%	37.5%	6.2%	100.0%
	5.0%	9.1%	11.4%	33.3%	7.1%	12.4%
Assistant Professor	8	8	23	2	2	43
	18.6%	18.6%	53.5%	4.7%	4.7%	100.0%
	40.0%	24.2%	52.3%	11.1%	14.3%	33.3%
Guest Faculty	6	4	2	1	3	16
	37.5%	25.0%	12.5%	6.2%	18.8%	100.0%
	30.0%	12.1%	4.5%	5.6%	21.4%	12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	3	16	9	6	5	39
	7.7%	41.0%	23.1%	15.4%	12.8%	100.0%
	15.0%	48.5%	20.5%	33.3%	35.7%	30.2%
Total	20	33	44	18	14	129
	15.5%	25.6%	34.1%	14.0%	10.9%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: None of the majority from any designation of academician falls in very high category i.e. there is a big room for improvement in Foreign Language skills across all the designation of academicians.

C) Academic designations and communication skills

The 43.4 percent of respondents assume that Communication Skills developed after the completion of tourism programs is *very high*. The highest to lowest percentage of respondents associated with *moderate* category are: Assistant Professor > Researcher > Guest faculty > Professors /Associate professor. The highest percentage among different levels of Communication Skills, 53.3 percent Professors, 46.5 percent Assistant Professors and 48.7 Researchers elicit the fact that communication skills are developed of high level among tourism graduates while 37.5 percent Guest Faculty assume that the skills are *moderately* imparted.

Table 5.54: Academic designations and communication

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across Communication skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	0 0.0% 0.0%	0 0.0% 0.0%	4 26.7% 8.9%	8 53.3% 14.3%	3 20.0% 27.3%	15 100.0% 11.6%
Associate Professor	3 18.8% 100.0%	3 18.8% 21.4%	4 25.0% 8.9%	4 25.0% 7.1%	2 12.5% 18.2%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Assistant Professor	0 0.0% 0.0%	2 4.7% 14.3%	19 44.2% 42.2%	20 46.5% 35.7%	2 4.7% 18.2%	43 100.0% 33.3%
Guest Faculty	0 0.0% 0.0%	2 12.5% 14.3%	6 37.5% 13.3%	5 31.2% 8.9%	3 18.8% 27.3%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	0 0.0% 0.0%	7 17.9% 50.0%	12 30.8% 26.7%	19 48.7% 33.9%	1 2.6% 9.1%	39 100.0% 30.2%
Total	3 2.3% 100.0%	14 10.9% 100.0%	45 34.9% 100.0%	56 43.4% 100.0%	11 8.5% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: None of the ‘majority’ from any designation of academicians falls in *very high* category.

D) Academic designations and Travel Software Skills

There are 38.8 percent respondents (which is highest) opined that Tourism Software skills *moderately* developed among tourism graduates after completion of discipline. The highest to lowest percentage of respondents associated with *moderate* category are: Assistant Professor> Researchers>Professor>Guest Faculty/Associate Professor

Table shows that, in the opinion of Professors (46.7), Assistant Professors (48.80 and Researchers (30.8) have opinion that Travel software skills are developed up to moderate level among tourism graduates. The Guest Faculty (37.5) have opinion that travel software skills are poorly incorporated. . Tourism industry is highly technology driven industry in 21st century. Human resources will lag behind in competition without specialized skills and expertise in travel software. (there is need

to launch programs like tourism and technology or digital marketing in tourism, Data mining and tourism, Use of AI in tourism).

Table 5.55: Academic designations and travel software skills

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across Travel Software Skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	0	1	7	4	3	15
	0.0%	6.7%	46.7%	26.7%	20.0%	100.0%
	0.0%	4.0%	14.0%	25.0%	14.3%	11.6%
Associate Professor	2	2	5	5	2	16
	12.5%	12.5%	31.2%	31.2%	12.5%	100.0%
	11.8%	8.0%	10.0%	31.2%	9.5%	12.4%
Assistant Professor	9	6	21	3	4	43
	20.9%	14.0%	48.8%	7.0%	9.3%	100.0%
	52.9%	24.0%	42.0%	18.8%	19.0%	33.3%
Guest Faculty	2	6	5	0	3	16
	12.5%	37.5%	31.2%	0.0%	18.8%	100.0%
	11.8%	24.0%	10.0%	0.0%	14.3%	12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	4	10	12	4	9	39
	10.3%	25.6%	30.8%	10.3%	23.1%	100.0%
	23.5%	40.0%	24.0%	25.0%	42.9%	30.2%
Total	17	25	50	16	21	129
	13.2%	19.4%	38.8%	12.4%	16.3%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: None of the ‘majority’ from any designation of academicians falls in very high category.

E) Academic designations and rating of Outdoor Skills

There are 29.5 percent respondents (which is highest) opined that Outdoor skill *moderately* and *highly* developed among tourism graduates after completion of discipline. It is assumed by the Guest Faculty (37.5) and Researchers (33.3) that Outdoor Activities exposure among tourism graduates infused are of *moderate level*. The Assistant Professors (39.5) opined it as *high* and Associate Professors (31.2) placed the skills at *very high*.

Tourism has many forms i.e. MICE, Event Management, Trade Fare, Sports, Adventure. These forms of tourism need very high category of outdoor skills among the staff. It can be enhanced through identification of students as per the interest and case study method on interest and then prepare the students accordingly, and place the

students in industry as per their interest during internships. Networking among same interest specialist.

Table 5.56: Academic designations and Outdoor Skills

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across outdoor Skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	0 0.0% 0.0%	0 0.0% 0.0%	6 40.0% 15.8%	3 20.0% 7.9%	6 40.0% 17.6%	15 100.0% 11.6%
Associate Professor	2 12.5% 28.6%	2 12.5% 16.7%	3 18.8% 7.9%	4 25.0% 10.5%	5 31.2% 14.7%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Assistant Professor	3 7.0% 42.9%	4 9.3% 33.3%	10 23.3% 26.3%	17 39.5% 44.7%	9 20.9% 26.5%	43 100.0% 33.3%
Guest Faculty	0 0.0% 0.0%	2 12.5% 16.7%	6 37.5% 15.8%	3 18.8% 7.9%	5 31.2% 14.7%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	2 5.1% 28.6%	4 10.3% 33.3%	13 33.3% 34.2%	11 28.2% 28.9%	9 23.1% 26.5%	39 100.0% 30.2%
Total	7 5.4% 100.0%	12 9.3% 100.0%	38 29.5% 100.0%	38 29.5% 100.0%	34 26.4% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: Professors, Associate Professors and Guest faculty majority fall in *very high* category. The Researches and Assistant Professors have a feeling to improve it up to next level.

F) Academic designations and Research Skills

There are 38.8 percent respondents (which is highest) opined that research skill *moderately* developed among tourism graduates after completion of program. The highest to lowest percentage of respondents associated with *moderate* category are: Assistant Professor/Researcher > Associate Professor > Guest Faculty > Professor

It is clear from the table that according to the responses of Associate Professors (50.0), Assistant Professors (37.2), Guest Faculty (43.8) and Researchers (41.0) Research skills among tourism graduates are *moderate*. The Professors (33.3) thinks that research skills are of *high* level among the tourism graduates at the time of completion of course.

Research attitude leads to innovation, diversification of products, creativity, entrepreneurship and quality of product. But lack of research skills will have adverse effect on tourism industry as whole not only tourism graduates. There is need to make it compulsory for UG/PG students to attend research conferences, paper publications, more tourism literature in departmental library, and every year department should organize a conference of research in tourism.

Table 5.57: Academic designations and Research Skills

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across research Skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	1 6.7% 5.9%	3 20.0% 11.5%	3 20.0% 6.0%	5 33.3% 22.7%	3 20.0% 21.4%	15 100.0% 11.6%
Associate Professor	3 18.8% 17.6%	1 6.2% 3.8%	8 50.0% 16.0%	2 12.5% 9.1%	2 12.5% 14.3%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Assistant Professor	6 14.0% 35.3%	10 23.3% 38.5%	16 37.2% 32.0%	7 16.3% 31.8%	4 9.3% 28.6%	43 100.0% 33.3%
Guest Faculty	4 25.0% 23.5%	3 18.8% 11.5%	7 43.8% 14.0%	1 6.2% 4.5%	1 6.2% 7.1%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	3 7.7% 17.6%	9 23.1% 34.6%	16 41.0% 32.0%	7 17.9% 31.8%	4 10.3% 28.6%	39 100.0% 30.2%
Total	17 13.2% 100.0%	26 20.2% 100.0%	50 38.8% 100.0%	22 17.1% 100.0%	14 10.9% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: None of the ‘majority’ from any designation of academicians falls in very high category.

G) Academic designations and Presentation skills

The majority of the percentage of responses from Associate Professors (37.5), Assistant Professors (62.8) and Research Scholars (48.7) expressed that Presentation Skills are incorporated up to a high level of professionalism. The Guest Faculty (31.2) and Professors (40.0) have the majority in favour that Presentation Skills are moderately developed among tourism graduates at the time of completion of course.

There are 47.3 percent respondents (which is highest) opined that Presentation Skills *highly* developed among tourism graduates after completion of program. The highest to lowest percentage of respondents associated with *high* category are: Assistant Professor > Researcher > Associate Professor > Professor > Guest Faculty.

Academia-industry network as well as internship of tourism academicians is needed, to produce contemporary human resources.

Table 5.58: Academic designations and Presentation Skills

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across presentation Skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	0	1	6	5	3	15
	0.0%	6.7%	40.0%	33.3%	20.0%	100.0%
	0.0%	6.2%	22.2%	8.2%	14.3%	11.6%
Associate Professor	3	3	1	6	3	16
	18.8%	18.8%	6.2%	37.5%	18.8%	100.0%
	75.0%	18.8%	3.7%	9.8%	14.3%	12.4%
Assistant Professor	1	5	6	27	4	43
	2.3%	11.6%	14.0%	62.8%	9.3%	100.0%
	25.0%	31.2%	22.2%	44.3%	19.0%	33.3%
Guest Faculty	0	3	5	4	4	16
	0.0%	18.8%	31.2%	25.0%	25.0%	100.0%
	0.0%	18.8%	18.5%	6.6%	19.0%	12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	0	4	9	19	7	39
	0.0%	10.3%	23.1%	48.7%	17.9%	100.0%
	0.0%	25.0%	33.3%	31.1%	33.3%	30.2%
Total	4	16	27	61	21	129
	3.1%	12.4%	20.9%	47.3%	16.3%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: None of the ‘majority’ from any designation of academicians falls in *very high* category.

H) Academic designations and Digital Skills

Table represents that 35.7 percent of academicians opined that digital skill has *infused* up to moderate level through tourism programs. The highest to lowest percentage of respondents associated with *moderate* category are: Researcher > Assistant Professor > Guest Faculty > Associate professor > Professor.

The Professors (40.0) and Assistant Professors (39.5) support high category while Guest Faculty (37.5) and Researchers (41.0) opined that Digital Skills are moderate in nature among the tourism graduates at the completion of course.

Tourism industry is booming and technology is one of the reasons, as through the use of digital skills product information can reach each client who is connected to digital media across the globe. Tourism World is highly competitive and dynamic.

Table 5.59: Academic designations and Digital Skills

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across Digital Skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	0	2	4	6	3	15
	0.0%	13.3%	26.7%	40.0%	20.0%	100.0%
	0.0%	10.5%	8.7%	16.2%	13.6%	11.6%
Associate Professor	0	3	5	3	5	16
	0.0%	18.8%	31.2%	18.8%	31.2%	100.0%
	0.0%	15.8%	10.9%	8.1%	22.7%	12.4%
Assistant Professor	1	5	15	17	5	43
	2.3%	11.6%	34.9%	39.5%	11.6%	100.0%
	20.0%	26.3%	32.6%	45.9%	22.7%	33.3%
Guest Faculty	2	2	6	4	2	16
	12.5%	12.5%	37.5%	25.0%	12.5%	100.0%
	40.0%	10.5%	13.0%	10.8%	9.1%	12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	2	7	16	7	7	39
	5.1%	17.9%	41.0%	17.9%	17.9%	100.0%
	40.0%	36.8%	34.8%	18.9%	31.8%	30.2%
Total	5	19	46	37	22	129
	3.9%	14.7%	35.7%	28.7%	17.1%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: None of the ‘majority’ from any designation of academicians (except associate professors) falls in very high category.

D) Academic designations and Sales Skills

Table conveys that as per the opinion of Professors (60.0), Associate Professors (31.2) and Assistant Professors (34.9) that sales skill infused among tourism graduates through tourism curriculum are of *high level*. There are 31.8 percent respondents (which is highest) opined that digital skill *highly* evolved among tourism graduates after completion of program. The highest to lowest percentage of respondents associated with *high* category are: Assistant professor > Professor>Researcher > Associate Professor > Guest Faculty

(Sale of the product is very essential for survival of any institution either education or industry. Sales desk has to sell as per the goals of company or director sales' instructions. The 23.3 percentage of academicians (cumulative percentage of very low and low) accepted that sales skills being imparted are not found suitable for industry or mismatch. Education institution needs to produce managers at UG/PG level instead of f manpower. Moreover, solution resides in case study, technology use and A-I network).

Table 5.60: Academic designations and Sales Skills

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across sales Skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	0 0.0% 0.0%	0 0.0% 0.0%	4 26.7% 10.5%	9 60.0% 22.0%	2 13.3% 10.0%	15 100.0% 11.6%
Associate Professor	1 6.2% 25.0%	3 18.8% 11.5%	3 18.8% 7.9%	5 31.2% 12.2%	4 25.0% 20.0%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Assistant Professor	1 2.3% 25.0%	7 16.3% 26.9%	14 32.6% 36.8%	15 34.9% 36.6%	6 14.0% 30.0%	43 100.0% 33.3%
Guest Faculty	1 6.2% 25.0%	4 25.0% 15.4%	4 25.0% 10.5%	4 25.0% 9.8%	3 18.8% 15.0%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	1 2.6% 25.0%	12 30.8% 46.2%	13 33.3% 34.2%	8 20.5% 19.5%	5 12.8% 25.0%	39 100.0% 30.2%
Total	4 3.1% 100.0%	26 20.2% 100.0%	38 29.5% 100.0%	41 31.8% 100.0%	20 15.5% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: None of the 'majority' from any designation of academicians falls in *very high* category.

J) Academic designations and Marketing Skills

Marketing of the product at right place, right market, right mode and right time. But contemporary marketing is dynamic in nature and context of marketing have changed as it was 20th century. The concept of Artificial Intelligence, Video marketing, virtual tour, data mining, machine learning, digital marketing and more; and its use have revolutionary changes. The digital marketing concept is a part of theory only in tourism education. In 21st century where tourism graduates are employed by aggregator companies, there is need to develop tourism programs with

use of technology, app development, use of AI in tourism and its applications. Otherwise tourism graduates wouldn't be able to become entrepreneur only employees.

It is interesting to know that Professors(46.7, Associate (37.5), Assistant Professors(34.9) and Guest Faculty (31.2) support the fact that Marketing Skills are *highly* ingrained in tourism graduated but Research Scholars contradict the fact that the ingrained Marketing Skills are moderate in nature.

The majority (34.9) of total respondents fall in *high* category. The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with *high* category are: Assistant professor > Researcher > Professor> Associate Professor> Guest Faculty.

Table 5.61: Academic designations and Marketing Skills

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across marketing Skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	0	1	4	7	3	15
	0.0%	6.7%	26.7%	46.7%	20.0%	100.0%
	0.0%	4.2%	10.5%	15.6%	16.7%	11.6%
Associate Professor	1	4	3	6	2	16
	6.2%	25.0%	18.8%	37.5%	12.5%	100.0%
	25.0%	16.7%	7.9%	13.3%	11.1%	12.4%
Assistant Professor	1	6	14	15	7	43
	2.3%	14.0%	32.6%	34.9%	16.3%	100.0%
	25.0%	25.0%	36.8%	33.3%	38.9%	33.3%
Guest Faculty	1	3	4	5	3	16
	6.2%	18.8%	25.0%	31.2%	18.8%	100.0%
	25.0%	12.5%	10.5%	11.1%	16.7%	12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	1	10	13	12	3	39
	2.6%	25.6%	33.3%	30.8%	7.7%	100.0%
	25.0%	41.7%	34.2%	26.7%	16.7%	30.2%
Total	4	24	38	45	18	129
	3.1%	18.6%	29.5%	34.9%	14.0%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: None of the 'majority' from any designation of academicians falls in very high category.

K) Academic designations and Tourism Industry Ethics

Literature has shown that responsible practices are important in tourism industry because now tourism companies are moving towards community welfare. There is need to produce human resource with ethical practices. Department must

have its own generic skills list and must be stick to the principles, it will not only produce ethically responsible human resource but also accountable to community and society. PDP (personality development program) on ethical practices in tourism industry, networking among those industries which are recognized as the bacon bearer of ethical practices. It will definitely lead towards the sustainability of tourism industry. It will make academia more responsible about humanity.

Table shows that 31.8 percent (which is highest) of academicians assume that tourism industry ethics skill imparted to tourism graduate are of *high* level. The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with *high* category are: Assistant professor > Researcher > Associate Professor> Professor > Guest Faculty

Tourism Industry Ethics are developed up to a very high standard among tourism graduates in the opinions of Guest Faculty (37.5), up to *High* standard according to Assistant Professors (41.9) and Researchers (33.3), and it was developed moderately according to the Professors (46.7).

Table 5.62: Academic designations and Tourism Industry Ethics Skills

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across Tourism industry Ethics Skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	1 6.7% 20.0%	0 0.0% 0.0%	7 46.7% 20.6%	4 26.7% 9.8%	3 20.0% 9.7%	15 100.0% 11.6%
Associate Professor	1 6.2% 20.0%	5 31.2% 27.8%	2 12.5% 5.9%	5 31.2% 12.2%	3 18.8% 9.7%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Assistant Professor	0 0.0% 0.0%	5 11.6% 27.8%	11 25.6% 32.4%	18 41.9% 43.9%	9 20.9% 29.0%	43 100.0% 33.3%
Guest Faculty	1 6.2% 20.0%	3 18.8% 16.7%	5 31.2% 14.7%	1 6.2% 2.4%	6 37.5% 19.4%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	2 5.1% 40.0%	5 12.8% 27.8%	9 23.1% 26.5%	13 33.3% 31.7%	10 25.6% 32.3%	39 100.0% 30.2%
Total	5 3.9% 100.0%	18 14.0% 100.0%	34 26.4% 100.0%	41 31.8% 100.0%	31 24.0% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: None of the ‘majority’ from any designation of academicians (except Guest faculty) falls in very high category.

L) Academic designations and Travel Ethics

It is the responsibility of tourism education to produce ethical travellers along with ethical tourism professionals. The 28.7 percent respondents mentioned they are able to produce human resource with travel Ethics with *moderate* category. The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with in *moderate* category are: Researcher >Assistant professor > Guest Faculty > Professor > Associate Professor.

Table shows that the majority of Associate professors (31.2) and Assistant Professors (39.5) support high category while Researchers (33.3) support moderately skills enhanced among tourism graduates.

Table 5.63: Academic designations and Travel Ethics Skills

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across Travel Ethics Skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	1 6.7% 16.7%	3 20.0% 15.0%	4 26.7% 10.8%	4 26.7% 11.4%	3 20.0% 9.7%	15 100.0% 11.6%
Associate Professor	1 6.2% 16.7%	4 25.0% 20.0%	3 18.8% 8.1%	5 31.2% 14.3%	3 18.8% 9.7%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Assistant Professor	1 2.3% 16.7%	5 11.6% 25.0%	11 25.6% 29.7%	17 39.5% 48.6%	9 20.9% 29.0%	43 100.0% 33.3%
Guest Faculty	2 12.5% 33.3%	1 6.2% 5.0%	6 37.5% 16.2%	1 6.2% 2.9%	6 37.5% 19.4%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	1 2.6% 16.7%	7 17.9% 35.0%	13 33.3% 35.1%	8 20.5% 22.9%	10 25.6% 32.3%	39 100.0% 30.2%
Total	6 4.7% 100.0%	20 15.5% 100.0%	37 28.7% 100.0%	35 27.1% 100.0%	31 24.0% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Key finding: None of the ‘majority’ from any designation of academicians (Guest Faculty) falls in very high category.

Overview: The majority for any of the academic designation doesn’t fall in *very high* category with regard to Communication, Foreign Language, Tourism Software, Research, Presentation, Sales and Marketing Skills.

5.12.2 Tourism professionals and Skills found

Table 5.49 to 5.49.5 reveals the opinion of tourism professionals (management level wise) about, level of Confidence Level (CL), Foreign Language, Communication, Travel Software, Outdoor, Research, Presentation, Digital, Sales, Marketing, Travel Ethics and Tourism Industry Ethics Skills developed in tourism graduates after completion of course and at the time of hiring. . The scaling of different Skills categorized as- Very Low (1); Low (2); Moderate (3); high (4) and Very High (5).

A) Level of Management and level of Confidence found at the time of hiring

It was found that the majority of respondents from Low Management (34.5), Middle Management (26.5) and Top Management (35.1) have opinion that at the time of hiring the skills pertaining to Confidence level were *very high*. The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with in *very high* category are: Low Management > Top Management > Middle Management.

Table 5.64: Management Level and Confidence level

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across level of confidence					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	2	4	15	17	20	58
	3.4%	6.9%	25.9%	29.3%	34.5%	100.0%
	28.6%	30.8%	50.0%	45.9%	47.6%	45.0%
Middle	3	6	8	8	9	34
	8.8%	17.6%	23.5%	23.5%	26.5%	100.0%
	42.9%	46.2%	26.7%	21.6%	21.4%	26.4%
Top	2	3	7	12	13	37
	5.4%	8.1%	18.9%	32.4%	35.1%	100.0%
	28.6%	23.1%	23.3%	32.4%	31.0%	28.7%
Total	7	13	30	37	42	129
	5.4%	10.1%	23.3%	28.7%	32.6%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

B) Level of Management and Foreign Language Skills found at the time of hiring

Table 5.65 shows the foreign language skills found among tourism graduates at the time of hiring in travel trade organization. Foreign language skills developed after completion of tourism program are placed at very low level by Middle Management (38.2), Top Management (45.9) and total respondents (34.9). The Low Management (32.8) have opinion that the skill are of low category. The highest to lowest percentage of respondents associated with in *very low* category are: Top Management >Low Management> Middle Management.

Table 5.65: Management Level and Foreign Language Skills

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across Foreign language					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	15	19	8	11	5	58
	25.9%	32.8%	13.8%	19.0%	8.6%	100.0%
	33.3%	59.4%	33.3%	64.7%	45.5%	45.0%
Middle	13	9	8	2	2	34
	38.2%	26.5%	23.5%	5.9%	5.9%	100.0%
	28.9%	28.1%	33.3%	11.8%	18.2%	26.4%
Top	17	4	8	4	4	37
	45.9%	10.8%	21.6%	10.8%	10.8%	100.0%
	37.8%	12.5%	33.3%	23.5%	36.4%	28.7%
Total	45	32	24	17	11	129
	34.9%	24.8%	18.6%	13.2%	8.5%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

C) Level of Management and Communication Skills at the time of hiring

The opinion of Top Management (32.4) and the majority (31.0) of total respondents have opinion that Communication skills at the time of hiring are found in *high category* among tourism graduates. The Low Management has a feeling that this particular skill is developed fully (very high) among tourism graduates. The highest to lowest percentage of respondents associated with in *high* category are: Low Management > Top Management > Middle Management.

Table 5.66: Management Level and Communication Skills

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across Communication skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	1	3	13	18	23	58
	1.7%	5.2%	22.4%	31.0%	39.7%	100.0%
	25.0%	20.0%	41.9%	45.0%	59.0%	45.0%
Middle	2	5	10	10	7	34
	5.9%	14.7%	29.4%	29.4%	20.6%	100.0%
	50.0%	33.3%	32.3%	25.0%	17.9%	26.4%
Top	1	7	8	12	9	37
	2.7%	18.9%	21.6%	32.4%	24.3%	100.0%
	25.0%	46.7%	25.8%	30.0%	23.1%	28.7%
Total	4	15	31	40	39	129
	3.1%	11.6%	24.0%	31.0%	30.2%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

D) Level of Management and Travel Software Skills at the time of hiring

The opinion of Low Management (37.9) and Top Management (29.7) is aligned with the opinion of majority (33.3) of total respondents with regards to Travel Software Skills i.e. *moderate*. The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with in *moderate* category are: Low Management > Top Management > Middle Management.

Tourism industry is highly technology driven industry in 21st century. Human resource will lag behind in competition without specialized skills and expertise in travel software. (there is need to launch programs like tourism and technology or digital marketing in tourism, Data mining and tourism, Use of AI in tourism).

Table 5.67: Management Level and Travel Software

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across travel software skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	13	11	22	10	2	58
	22.4%	19.0%	37.9%	17.2%	3.4%	100.0%
	41.9%	39.3%	51.2%	52.6%	25.0%	45.0%
Middle	8	10	10	4	2	34
	23.5%	29.4%	29.4%	11.8%	5.9%	100.0%
	25.8%	35.7%	23.3%	21.1%	25.0%	26.4%
Top	10	7	11	5	4	37
	27.0%	18.9%	29.7%	13.5%	10.8%	100.0%
	32.3%	25.0%	25.6%	26.3%	50.0%	28.7%
Total	31	28	43	19	8	129
	24.0%	21.7%	33.3%	14.7%	6.2%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

E) Level of Management and level of Outdoor Skills at the time of hiring

Majority of respondents i.e. 45.7 percent opined the skills as *moderately* nourished among the tourism graduates. The percentage among different levels of Management in support of *moderately* infused skills are as 55.2 from Low Management, 41.2 from Middle Management and 35.1 from Top management. The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with in *moderate* category are: Low Management > Middle Management > Top Management.

Tourism has many forms i.e. MICE, Event Management, Trade Fare, Sports, Adventure. These forms of tourism need very high category of outdoor skills among the staff. (it can be enhanced through identification of students as per the interest and case study method on interest and then prepare the students accordingly, and place the students in industry as per their interest during internships. Networking among same interest specialist).

Table 5.68: Management Level and Outdoor Skills

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across Outdoor Skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	1	6	32	14	5	58
	1.7%	10.3%	55.2%	24.1%	8.6%	100.0%
	7.1%	25.0%	54.2%	60.9%	55.6%	45.0%
Middle	7	8	14	2	3	34
	20.6%	23.5%	41.2%	5.9%	8.8%	100.0%
	50.0%	33.3%	23.7%	8.7%	33.3%	26.4%
Top	6	10	13	7	1	37
	16.2%	27.0%	35.1%	18.9%	2.7%	100.0%
	42.9%	41.7%	22.0%	30.4%	11.1%	28.7%
Total	14	24	59	23	9	129
	10.9%	18.6%	45.7%	17.8%	7.0%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

F) Level of Management and level of Research Skills at the time of hiring

Table shows that the opinion of majority of respondents (39.7) from Low management resemble the majority (32.6) of total respondents that the concerned Skill is *moderately* ingrained in tourism graduates at the time of hiring. It was also found that Middle management (29.4) and Top Management (35.1) rated the skill at *low*

level. The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with in *moderate* category are: Low Management > Top Management > Middle Management.

Research attitude leads to innovation, diversification of products, creativity, entrepreneurship and quality of product. But lack of research skills will have adverse effect on tourism industry as whole not only tourism graduates. Tourism industry has become a highly competitive sector and highly depend upon quality research and development.(There is need to make it compulsory for UG/PG students to attend research conferences, paper publication, more tourism literature in departmental library, and every year department should organize a conference of research in tourism).

Table 5.69: Management Level and Research Skills

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across Research Skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	8	16	23	10	1	58
	13.8%	27.6%	39.7%	17.2%	1.7%	100.0%
	34.8%	41.0%	54.8%	45.5%	33.3%	45.0%
Middle	9	10	9	6	0	34
	26.5%	29.4%	26.5%	17.6%	0.0%	100.0%
	39.1%	25.6%	21.4%	27.3%	0.0%	26.4%
Top	6	13	10	6	2	37
	16.2%	35.1%	27.0%	16.2%	5.4%	100.0%
	26.1%	33.3%	23.8%	27.3%	66.7%	28.7%
Total	23	39	42	22	3	129
	17.8%	30.2%	32.6%	17.1%	2.3%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

G) Level of Management and rating of Presentation skills at the time of hiring

The 33.3 percent of total tourism professionals responded that tourism graduates have *high* presentation skills. The Low Management (33.3) is streamed along the opinion of majority of tourism professionals. The Top Management and Middle Management have opined that Presentational Skills, found in tourism graduates are poor (low).

The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with in *high* category are: Low Management > Top Management > Middle Management.

Tourism industry is a service industry, moreover lack of Presentation Skills not good sign for academia as well as industry. Hence, academia-industry network as well as internship of tourism academicians is needed, to produce contemporary human resource.

Table 5.70: Management level and Presentation Skills

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across presentation skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	3	8	14	23	10	58
	5.2%	13.8%	24.1%	39.7%	17.2%	100.0%
	33.3%	47.1%	34.1%	53.5%	52.6%	45.0%
Middle	3	5	15	9	2	34
	8.8%	14.7%	44.1%	26.5%	5.9%	100.0%
	33.3%	29.4%	36.6%	20.9%	10.5%	26.4%
Top	3	4	12	11	7	37
	8.1%	10.8%	32.4%	29.7%	18.9%	100.0%
	33.3%	23.5%	29.3%	25.6%	36.8%	28.7%
Total	9	17	41	43	19	129
	7.0%	13.2%	31.8%	33.3%	14.7%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

H) Level of Management and rating of Digital Skills at the time of hiring

The majority of respondents i.e. 29.5 percent of total tourism professionals with respect to *Digital Skills*, placed tourism graduates in *moderate* category. The Low Management (25.9) and Top Management (29.7) have favoured the decision of majority of total respondents. Meanwhile, Middle Management (38.2) rated the skill incorporated as poor (low). The highest to lowest percentage of tourism professionals associated with in *moderate* category are: Low Management > Middle Management > Top Management.

Tourism industry is booming and technology is one of the reasons, as through the use of digital skills product information can reach each client who is connected to digital media across the globe. There is need to incorporate tourism discipline like Tourism and Technology.

Table 5.71: Management Level and Digital Skills

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across digital skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	8	14	15	10	11	58
	13.8%	24.1%	25.9%	17.2%	19.0%	100.0%
	44.4%	41.2%	39.5%	41.7%	73.3%	45.0%
Middle	3	13	12	5	1	34
	8.8%	38.2%	35.3%	14.7%	2.9%	100.0%
	16.7%	38.2%	31.6%	20.8%	6.7%	26.4%
Top	7	7	11	9	3	37
	18.9%	18.9%	29.7%	24.3%	8.1%	100.0%
	38.9%	20.6%	28.9%	37.5%	20.0%	28.7%
Total	18	34	38	24	15	129
	14.0%	26.4%	29.5%	18.6%	11.6%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

I) Level of Management and rating of Sales Skills at the time of hiring

According to the opinion of tourism professionals’ majority (29.5 percent) the Sales Skills are found desirable (very high) among tourism graduates at the time of hiring. The Low Management (36.2 percent) and Top Management (27.0 percent) are along the majority of total respondents while Middle Management (32.4 percent) is against the majority of total respondents opined that skills are poorly incorporated among tourism graduates. The highest to lowest percentage of tourism professionals associated with in *very high* category are: Low Management > Top Management > Middle Management.

Sales Skills of students come after completions of the course. Sale of the product is very essential for survival of any institution either education or industry. Sales desk has to sell as per the goals of company or director sales’ instructions. Moreover, solution resides in case study, technology use and A-I network.

Table 5.72: Management Level and Sales Skills

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across sales skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	5	8	13	11	21	58
	8.6%	13.8%	22.4%	19.0%	36.2%	100.0%
	33.3%	47.1%	43.3%	37.9%	55.3%	45.0%
Middle	4	3	11	9	7	34
	11.8%	8.8%	32.4%	26.5%	20.6%	100.0%
	26.7%	17.6%	36.7%	31.0%	18.4%	26.4%
Top	6	6	6	9	10	37
	16.2%	16.2%	16.2%	24.3%	27.0%	100.0%
	40.0%	35.3%	20.0%	31.0%	26.3%	28.7%
Total	15	17	30	29	38	129
	11.6%	13.2%	23.3%	22.5%	29.5%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

J) Level of Management and rating of Marketing Skills at the time of hiring

The majority (27.9 percent) of tourism professionals and Top Management (29.7 percent) rated the Marketing Skills of students at the time of hiring in *high* category. The Middle Management (35.3 percent) is against the majority and placed the skills in *moderate* category.

Marketing of the product at right place, right market, right mode and right time. But contemporary marketing is dynamic in nature and context of marketing have changed as it was 20th century. The concept of Artificial Intelligence, Video marketing, virtual tour, data mining, machine learning, digital marketing and more; and its use has put the marketing trends on evolution. The digital marketing concept is a part of theory only in tourism education. In 21st century where tourism graduates as employed by aggregator companies, there is need to develop tourism programs with use of technology, app development, use of AI in tourism and its applications. Otherwise tourism graduates wouldn't be able to become entrepreneur only employees.

Table 5.73: Management level and Marketing Skills

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across marketing skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	5	8	16	16	13	58
	8.6%	13.8%	27.6%	27.6%	22.4%	100.0%
	31.2%	44.4%	47.1%	44.4%	52.0%	45.0%
Middle	4	5	12	9	4	34
	11.8%	14.7%	35.3%	26.5%	11.8%	100.0%
	25.0%	27.8%	35.3%	25.0%	16.0%	26.4%
Top	7	5	6	11	8	37
	18.9%	13.5%	16.2%	29.7%	21.6%	100.0%
	43.8%	27.8%	17.6%	30.6%	32.0%	28.7%
Total	16	18	34	36	25	129
	12.4%	14.0%	26.4%	27.9%	19.4%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

K) Level of Management and rating of Tourism Industry Ethics Skills at the time of hiring

In table 5.74, the 27.9 percent respondents found produced human resource with Tourism Industry Ethics Skills in *moderate* category. The Top (32.4 percent) and Low Management (37.9 percent) have a feeling that tourism graduates get unfused with high and very high level of Tourism Industry Ethics while Middle Management (32.4 percent) agreed with majority of total tourism respondents' responses. The highest to lowest percentage of tourism professionals associated with in *moderate* category are: Low Management > Top Management/Middle Management.

Table 5.74: Management Level and Tourism Industry Ethics Skills

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across tourism industry ethics skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	4	5	14	13	22	58
	6.9%	8.6%	24.1%	22.4%	37.9%	100.0%
	33.3%	27.8%	38.9%	39.4%	73.3%	45.0%
Middle	3	8	11	8	4	34
	8.8%	23.5%	32.4%	23.5%	11.8%	100.0%
	25.0%	44.4%	30.6%	24.2%	13.3%	26.4%
Top	5	5	11	12	4	37
	13.5%	13.5%	29.7%	32.4%	10.8%	100.0%
	41.7%	27.8%	30.6%	36.4%	13.3%	28.7%
Total	12	18	36	33	30	129
	9.3%	14.0%	27.9%	25.6%	23.3%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

L) Level of Management and rating of Travel Ethics Skills at the time of hiring

The Top Management (40.5 percent) and Middle Management (29.4 percent) have found Travel Ethics at *very high* and *moderate* level among the tourism graduates at the time of hiring. 29.5 percent of total respondents and low level management (36.2 percent) marked that they found high level of travel ethics among tourism graduates at the time of hiring. The highest to lowest percentage of tourism professionals associated with in *high* category are: Low Management > Top Management > Middle Management.

It is also the responsibility of tourism education and tourism industry to produce ethical travellers along with ethical tourism professionals.

Table 5.75: Tourism professionals and Travel Ethics Skills

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across travel ethics skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	2	8	15	21	12	58
	3.4%	13.8%	25.9%	36.2%	20.7%	100.0%
	22.2%	50.0%	48.4%	55.3%	34.3%	45.0%
Middle	2	6	10	8	8	34
	5.9%	17.6%	29.4%	23.5%	23.5%	100.0%
	22.2%	37.5%	32.3%	21.1%	22.9%	26.4%
Top	5	2	6	9	15	37
	13.5%	5.4%	16.2%	24.3%	40.5%	100.0%
	55.6%	12.5%	19.4%	23.7%	42.9%	28.7%
Total	9	16	31	38	35	129
	7.0%	12.4%	24.0%	29.5%	27.1%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Overview: In *very high* category of rating of skill found among tourism graduates at the time of hiring, there is no majority from any level of management towards Foreign Language, Tourism Software, Outdoor activities, Research, Presentation, Digital and Marketing skills.

5.13 Crosstab Analysis about Desired Level of Improvement in Tourism Education Content

It found that tourism professionals and academicians desire a level of improvement or change in tourism education contents to produce ideal tourism professionals in the country. In this regard, opinions of respondents are tabled here.

The Frequent syllabus Update (FSU), Industry Interaction (II), Job Training (JT), Research (Res.), Foreign Language (FL), Tourism Software (TS), Digital Skills (DS), Library Resources (LR), Academia-Industry Network (AIN) and Student Exchange Programs (SEP) are the areas of concern in this study.

5.13.1 Academicians

It deals with the opinion of academicians (designation wise) about level of improvements/changes required in ‘curriculum content’ to deliver ideal tourism education in India and consequently quality tourism professionals.

A) Academic designation and Frequent Syllabus Update

The majority of academicians i.e. 33.3 percent opined that there is *moderate* requirement of change in Frequent Syllabus Update to improve tourism education in India. This trend is also found in majority among sub-category of academic respondents i.e. Associate Professors (62.5) and Assistant Professors (37.2). The Guest Faculty (43.8) and Researcher (30.8.) are in favour of remarkable (very high) change in ‘syllabus update’. The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with *moderate* category are: Assistant Professor > Researchers > Associate Professor > Professor > Guest Faculty.

Tables 5.76: Academicians and Syllabus Update

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across Frequent Syllabus update					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	0	2	5	3	5	15
	0.0%	13.3%	33.3%	20.0%	33.3%	100.0%
	0.0%	11.8%	11.6%	10.3%	14.7%	11.6%
Associate Professor	1	1	10	1	3	16
	6.2%	6.2%	62.5%	6.2%	18.8%	100.0%
	16.7%	5.9%	23.3%	3.4%	8.8%	12.4%
Assistant Professor	2	5	16	13	7	43
	4.7%	11.6%	37.2%	30.2%	16.3%	100.0%
	33.3%	29.4%	37.2%	44.8%	20.6%	33.3%
Guest Faculty	3	0	1	5	7	16
	18.8%	0.0%	6.2%	31.2%	43.8%	100.0%
	50.0%	0.0%	2.3%	17.2%	20.6%	12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	0	9	11	7	12	39
	0.0%	23.1%	28.2%	17.9%	30.8%	100.0%
	0.0%	52.9%	25.6%	24.1%	35.3%	30.2%
Total	6	17	43	29	34	129
	4.7%	13.2%	33.3%	22.5%	26.4%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

B) Academic designation and Industry Interaction

The majority of academic respondents (31.8 percent) opined that Industry-Interaction is *very highly* important to give a makeover to present tourism education in the country. The highest percentage of opinion with in the category of academician i.e. Professor (40 percent) and Associate Professor (37.5 percent) think there is *moderate* need of Industry-Interaction to deliver quality tourism education. The Researchers (35.9 percent) and Guest Faculty (50.0 percent) feel very high rate of improvement to impart quality tourism education. The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with *very high* category (out of total respondents in very high category) are: Researcher >Assistant professor/Guest Faculty > Associate Professor > Professor.

Tables 5.77: Academicians and Industry-Interaction

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across Industry interaction					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	-	0 0.0% 0.0%	6 40.0% 16.7%	3 20.0% 7.7%	6 40.0% 14.6%	15 100.0% 11.6%
Associate Professor	-	0 0.0% 0.0%	6 37.5% 16.7%	5 31.2% 12.8%	5 31.2% 12.2%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Assistant Professor	-	4 9.3% 30.8%	12 27.9% 33.3%	19 44.2% 48.7%	8 18.6% 19.5%	43 100.0% 33.3%
Guest Faculty	-	2 12.5% 15.4%	3 18.8% 8.3%	3 18.8% 7.7%	8 50.0% 19.5%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	-	7 17.9% 53.8%	9 23.1% 25.0%	9 23.1% 23.1%	14 35.9% 34.1%	39 100.0% 30.2%
Total	-	13 10.1% 100.0%	36 27.9% 100.0%	39 30.2% 100.0%	41 31.8% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

C) Academic designation and Job Training

Job training is an important component of tourism education curriculum. The majority of total respondents (34.9 percent) are supported by Researchers (35.9 percent) and Guest Faculty (56.2 percent) that there is very high need to change

current Job Training practices in the country. The Professors (40.0 percent) and Assistant Professors (41.9 percent) feel *high* requirement while Associate Professors have opinion to incorporate *moderate* changes.

The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with *very high* category (out of total respondents in very high category) are: Researcher >Assistant professor >Guest Faculty > Associate Professor > Professor.

Tables 5.78: Academicians and Job Training

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across Job training					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	0	0	5	6	4	15
	0.0%	0.0%	33.3%	40.0%	26.7%	100.0%
	0.0%	0.0%	21.7%	14.6%	8.9%	11.6%
Associate Professor	2	0	7	2	5	16
	12.5%	0.0%	43.8%	12.5%	31.2%	100.0%
	50.0%	0.0%	30.4%	4.9%	11.1%	12.4%
Assistant Professor	2	8	2	18	13	43
	4.7%	18.6%	4.7%	41.9%	30.2%	100.0%
	50.0%	50.0%	8.7%	43.9%	28.9%	33.3%
Guest Faculty	0	4	2	1	9	16
	0.0%	25.0%	12.5%	6.2%	56.2%	100.0%
	0.0%	25.0%	8.7%	2.4%	20.0%	12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	0	4	7	14	14	39
	0.0%	10.3%	17.9%	35.9%	35.9%	100.0%
	0.0%	25.0%	30.4%	34.1%	31.1%	30.2%
Total	4	16	23	41	45	129
	3.1%	12.4%	17.8%	31.8%	34.9%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

D) Academic designation and Research Skills

While among all academicians, 35.7 percent opined that there is *high* role of Research Skills to improve tourism education in India. It was also found Professor (40.0 percent), Assistant Professors (46.5 percent) and Researcher (33.3 percent) do favour the thoughts of majority of academicians. The Associate Professors (56.2 percent) have a feeling the Research Skills need *moderate* improvement while Guest Faculty (37.5 percent) thought it requires giant (*very high*) reforms to deliver ideal tourism education. The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with

very high category (out of total respondents in very high category) are: Assistant professor > Researcher > Professor> Guest Faculty > Associate Professor.

To improve the research component it is necessary to teach research subjects allied to tourism rather than pure research subjects, to establish research head with the collaboration of industry, government and community. Moreover, research problems must be action based, time bound solutions to the problems of stakeholders. The compulsion to have departmental journal and research publication to graduate and postgraduate level students and research topic regarding the interest of future jobs Research Skills.

Tables 5.79: Academicians and Research

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across Research					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	0 0.0% 0.0%	2 13.3% 20.0%	5 33.3% 11.4%	6 40.0% 13.0%	2 13.3% 7.4%	15 100.0% 11.6%
Associate Professor	1 6.2% 50.0%	2 12.5% 20.0%	9 56.2% 20.5%	2 12.5% 4.3%	2 12.5% 7.4%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Assistant Professor	1 2.3% 50.0%	2 4.7% 20.0%	14 32.6% 31.8%	20 46.5% 43.5%	6 14.0% 22.2%	43 100.0% 33.3%
Guest Faculty	0 0.0% 0.0%	0 0.0% 0.0%	5 31.2% 11.4%	5 31.2% 10.9%	6 37.5% 22.2%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	0 0.0% 0.0%	4 10.3% 40.0%	11 28.2% 25.0%	13 33.3% 28.3%	11 28.2% 40.7%	39 100.0% 30.2%
Total	2 1.6% 100.0%	10 7.8% 100.0%	44 34.1% 100.0%	46 35.7% 100.0%	27 20.9% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

E) Academic designation and Foreign Language

The highest percentage of opinion among all the academician is 34.9 and favours moderate improvement for Foreign Language. This fact is also supported by Professors (53.3 percent) Associate Professors (37.5 percent) and Researchers (38.5 percent). The Assistant professors (39.5 percent) and Guest Faculty (50.0 percent) thinks that Foreign Language requires *high* change to lead the tourism education

towards quality education. The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with *moderate* category are: Researcher > Assistant Professor > Professor > Associate Professor > Guest Faculty

Tables 5.80: Academicians and Foreign Language

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across foreign language					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	1 6.7% 10.0%	2 13.3% 16.7%	8 53.3% 17.8%	3 20.0% 7.5%	1 6.7% 4.5%	15 100.0% 11.6%
Associate Professor	4 25.0% 40.0%	1 6.2% 8.3%	6 37.5% 13.3%	2 12.5% 5.0%	3 18.8% 13.6%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Assistant Professor	5 11.6% 50.0%	3 7.0% 25.0%	11 25.6% 24.4%	17 39.5% 42.5%	7 16.3% 31.8%	43 100.0% 33.3%
Guest Faculty	0 0.0% 0.0%	0 0.0% 0.0%	5 31.2% 11.1%	8 50.0% 20.0%	3 18.8% 13.6%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	0 0.0% 0.0%	6 15.4% 50.0%	15 38.5% 33.3%	10 25.6% 25.0%	8 20.5% 36.4%	39 100.0% 30.2%
Total	10 7.8% 100.0%	12 9.3% 100.0%	45 34.9% 100.0%	40 31.0% 100.0%	22 17.1% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

F) Academic designation and Travel Software Training

Tourism academicians have responded with the highest percentage of 30.2 in *high category* with a felt need for tourism software training. Tourism industry demands wide knowledge about different applications and the software for the smooth running of industry. The fact is supported by the opinion of Guest Faculty (50.0 percent) and Researchers (35.9 percent) in ‘high category’ of improvement in current tourism education curriculum. The Associate Professors (56.2 percent) replied moderate need of improvement while Professors (40.0 percent) and Assistant Professors (44.2 percent) have a feeling of *high* need for improvement in Travel Software training to make tourism education closer to industry demand. The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with *high* category (out of total

respondents in individual category of academicians) are: Assistant professor > Researcher > Professor > Guest Faculty > Associate Professor.

Table 5.81: Academicians and Travel Software Training

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across Tourism Software Training					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	1 6.7% 11.1%	0 0.0% 0.0%	6 40.0% 17.6%	6 40.0% 15.4%	2 13.3% 5.9%	15 100.0% 11.6%
Associate Professor	1 6.2% 11.1%	3 18.8% 23.1%	9 56.2% 26.5%	2 12.5% 5.1%	1 6.2% 2.9%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Assistant Professor	6 14.0% 66.7%	1 2.3% 7.7%	8 18.6% 23.5%	19 44.2% 48.7%	9 20.9% 26.5%	43 100.0% 33.3%
Guest Faculty	0 0.0% 0.0%	1 6.2% 7.7%	3 18.8% 8.8%	4 25.0% 10.3%	8 50.0% 23.5%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	1 2.6% 11.1%	8 20.5% 61.5%	8 20.5% 23.5%	8 20.5% 20.5%	14 35.9% 41.2%	39 100.0% 30.2%
Total	9 7.0% 100.0%	13 10.1% 100.0%	34 26.4% 100.0%	39 30.2% 100.0%	34 26.4% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

G) Academic designation and Digital Skills

30.2 percent (which is highest) of total respondents opined that there is *moderate* need of digital skills to improve tourism education in India. With regards to Digital Skills, Professors (46.7 percent), Associate Professors (43.8 percent) and Researchers (35.9 percent) in majority feel that *moderate* improvement in concerned component of curriculum. The Assistant Professors and Guest faculty demand *high* and *very high* improvement in Digital Skills part of the syllabus to compete the world destinations. The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with *Moderate* category (out of total respondents in individual category of academicians) are: Researcher > Professor/ Associate Professor/ Assistant Professor > Guest Faculty.

This gap can be bridged through incorporation of contemporary technology and its practical use in tourism industry, product development, marketing and sustainable development.

Table 5.82: Academicians and Digital Skills

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across digital skills in Tourism					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	0	1	7	6	1	15
	0.0%	6.7%	46.7%	40.0%	6.7%	100.0%
	0.0%	7.7%	17.9%	16.7%	2.7%	11.6%
Associate Professor	0	4	7	3	2	16
	0.0%	25.0%	43.8%	18.8%	12.5%	100.0%
	0.0%	30.8%	17.9%	8.3%	5.4%	12.4%
Assistant Professor	2	4	7	17	13	43
	4.7%	9.3%	16.3%	39.5%	30.2%	100.0%
	50.0%	30.8%	17.9%	47.2%	35.1%	33.3%
Guest Faculty	0	1	4	3	8	16
	0.0%	6.2%	25.0%	18.8%	50.0%	100.0%
	0.0%	7.7%	10.3%	8.3%	21.6%	12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	2	3	14	7	13	39
	5.1%	7.7%	35.9%	17.9%	33.3%	100.0%
	50.0%	23.1%	35.9%	19.4%	35.1%	30.2%
Total	4	13	39	36	37	129
	3.1%	10.1%	30.2%	27.9%	28.7%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

H) Academic designation and Library Resources

It was found from below mentioned table that except Professors rest all have opinion that library resources have to be improved up to a large (high category) extent. The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with *very high* category (out of total respondents in individual category of academicians) are: Assistant professor > Researcher > Guest Faculty > Associate Professor > Professor.

Table 5.83: Academicians and Library Resources

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across Library resources					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	0	1	6	5	3	15
	0.0%	6.7%	40.0%	33.3%	20.0%	100.0%
	0.0%	8.3%	18.2%	9.6%	10.0%	11.6%
Associate Professor	0	2	6	6	2	16
	0.0%	12.5%	37.5%	37.5%	12.5%	100.0%
	0.0%	16.7%	18.2%	11.5%	6.7%	12.4%
Assistant Professor	0	5	10	18	10	43
	0.0%	11.6%	23.3%	41.9%	23.3%	100.0%
	0.0%	41.7%	30.3%	34.6%	33.3%	33.3%
Guest Faculty	0	1	5	7	3	16
	0.0%	6.2%	31.2%	43.8%	18.8%	100.0%
	0.0%	8.3%	15.2%	13.5%	10.0%	12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	2	3	6	16	12	39
	5.1%	7.7%	15.4%	41.0%	30.8%	100.0%
	100.0%	25.0%	18.2%	30.8%	40.0%	30.2%
Total	2	12	33	52	30	129
	1.6%	9.3%	25.6%	40.3%	23.3%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

D) Academic designation and Academia-Industry Network

The majority (40.3 percent) from total respondents, Assistant Professors (37.2 percent), Guest Faculty (56.2 percent) and Researchers (46.2 percent) have recognised that Academia-Industry networking have very important role in quality tourism education and need to revise it at *very high* context of improvement to produce quality human resources. The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with *very high* category (out of total respondents in individual category of academicians) are: Assistant professor > Researcher > Guest Faculty > Professor > Associate Professor.

Tourism industry is zestful in nature. Through academic-industry interaction (A-II) tourism education can be transmitted as per the requirements of shareholders. This interaction can be practiced through Alumni meets, conferences, industry lectures, participation of industry professionals in syllabus design and industry sponsored research internship for academicians in industry, networking at regional, national and international level.

Table 5.84: Academicians and Academia-Industry Training

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across Academia Industry Training					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	0 0.0% 0.0%	0 0.0% 0.0%	7 46.7% 18.4%	3 20.0% 10.3%	5 33.3% 9.6%	15 100.0% 11.6%
Associate Professor	0 0.0% 0.0%	2 12.5% 28.6%	6 37.5% 15.8%	4 25.0% 13.8%	4 25.0% 7.7%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Assistant Professor	2 4.7% 66.7%	1 2.3% 14.3%	10 23.3% 26.3%	14 32.6% 48.3%	16 37.2% 30.8%	43 100.0% 33.3%
Guest Faculty	0 0.0% 0.0%	1 6.2% 14.3%	3 18.8% 7.9%	3 18.8% 10.3%	9 56.2% 17.3%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	1 2.6% 33.3%	3 7.7% 42.9%	12 30.8% 31.6%	5 12.8% 17.2%	18 46.2% 34.6%	39 100.0% 30.2%
Total	3 2.3% 100.0%	7 5.4% 100.0%	38 29.5% 100.0%	29 22.5% 100.0%	52 40.3% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

J) Academic designation and Student Exchange Programs

The 40.3 percent agreed that there is *very high* need to incorporate Student Exchange Program for quality tourism education to the country. The incorporation of Student exchange programs is very highly demanded across all the below mentioned designations of academicians except Associate Professors, they feel moderate requirement.

The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with *very high* category (out of total respondents in individual category of academicians) are: Guest Faculty > Assistant professor > Professor > Researcher > Associate Professor.

As per the literature review, political, cultural and geographic understanding about a destination is key to success of tourism professionals. Because a destination, politically stable and liberal, culturally diverse and geographically accessible, leads to economic development and wellbeing of host community. It was found during research that only Department of Tourism Studies, Pondicherry University offers student exchange program to the master students but it is limited in numbers. Collaboration with destinations which have exemplary tourism model and university

or institutions which have command over specific tourism domain will make it fruitful for the future tourism professionals.

Table 5.85: Academicians and Student Exchange Programs

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across student exchange program					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	1 6.7% 11.1%	1 6.7% 7.1%	2 13.3% 7.4%	5 33.3% 18.5%	6 40.0% 11.5%	15 100.0% 11.6%
Associate Professor	1 6.2% 11.1%	3 18.8% 21.4%	7 43.8% 25.9%	3 18.8% 11.1%	2 12.5% 3.8%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Assistant Professor	4 9.3% 44.4%	2 4.7% 14.3%	8 18.6% 29.6%	10 23.3% 37.0%	19 44.2% 36.5%	43 100.0% 33.3%
Guest Faculty	0 0.0% 0.0%	0 0.0% 0.0%	4 25.0% 14.8%	1 6.2% 3.7%	11 68.8% 21.2%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	3 7.7% 33.3%	8 20.5% 57.1%	6 15.4% 22.2%	8 20.5% 29.6%	14 35.9% 26.9%	39 100.0% 30.2%
Total	9 7.0% 100.0%	14 10.9% 100.0%	27 20.9% 100.0%	27 20.9% 100.0%	52 40.3% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Overview: Study shows that Library Resources and foreign language have no majority from any academic designation in favour of change at *very high* level. It was found at least The Guest Faculty and Researchers are common designation towards *very high* change or improvement in Research Skills, Tourism Software training, Digital skills, Academic-Industry Network and Student Exchange programs.

5.13.2 Tourism Professionals

It deals with the opinions of tourism professionals (management level wise) about level of improvements/changes required in ‘curriculum content’ to deliver ideal tourism education in India and consequently quality tourism professionals. The Frequent syllabus Update (FSU), Industry Interaction (II), Job Training (JT),

Research (Res.), Foreign Language (FL), Tourism Software (TS), Digital Skills (DS), Library Resources (LR), Academia-Industry Network (AIN) and Student Exchange Programs (SEP) are the areas of concern in this part.

A) Level of Management and Frequent Syllabus Update

Table shows that 41.1.percent tourism professionals lined up the improvement in Frequent Syllabus Update in very high category and supported by Top (37.8 percent) and Low Management (50.0 percent). The Middle Management (38.2 percent) favours moderate changes in the concerned area to produce ideal tourism professionals in the country. The highest to lowest percentage of professionals associated with *very high* rating (out of total respondents in individual category of industry professionals) of Frequent Syllabus Update for the benefit of tourism curriculum are: Low management > top management > middle management

Tables 5.86: Management and Frequent Syllabus Update

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across frequent syllabus update					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	4	3	14	8	29	58
	6.9%	5.2%	24.1%	13.8%	50.0%	100.0%
	50.0%	37.5%	36.8%	36.4%	54.7%	45.0%
Middle	3	2	13	6	10	34
	8.8%	5.9%	38.2%	17.6%	29.4%	100.0%
	37.5%	25.0%	34.2%	27.3%	18.9%	26.4%
Top	1	3	11	8	14	37
	2.7%	8.1%	29.7%	21.6%	37.8%	100.0%
	12.5%	37.5%	28.9%	36.4%	26.4%	28.7%
Total	8	8	38	22	53	129
	6.2%	6.2%	29.5%	17.1%	41.1%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

B) Level of Management and Industry-Interaction

Table 5.87 talks about interaction between tourism education institution and industry. Table shows that majority of tourism professionals (47.3 percent) mentioned the necessity for industry interaction among different at *very high* level. Among different levels of management i.e. Top (48.6 percent), Middle (38.2) and Low (51.7

percent), levels have opined that concerned skill have *very high* contribution in producing ideal tourism professionals and need to make appropriate changes in the same. The highest to lowest percentage of professionals associated with *very high* rating (out of total respondents in individual category of industry professionals) of industry interaction for the benefit of tourism curriculum are: Low management > top management > middle management.

Tables 5.87: Management and Industry-Interaction

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across industry interaction skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	2	5	7	14	30	58
	3.4%	8.6%	12.1%	24.1%	51.7%	100.0%
	33.3%	45.5%	31.8%	48.3%	49.2%	45.0%
Middle	1	3	8	9	13	34
	2.9%	8.8%	23.5%	26.5%	38.2%	100.0%
	16.7%	27.3%	36.4%	31.0%	21.3%	26.4%
Top	3	3	7	6	18	37
	8.1%	8.1%	18.9%	16.2%	48.6%	100.0%
	50.0%	27.3%	31.8%	20.7%	29.5%	28.7%
Total	6	11	22	29	61	129
	4.7%	8.5%	17.1%	22.5%	47.3%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

C) *Level of Management and Job Training*

The majority of respondents from Low Management (46.6 percent) opined support *very high*, Middle Management (35.3 percent) favour *moderate* and Top Management (43.2 percent) feels Job Training is *highly* needed for requisite change in tourism education across the country to give rise to quality professionals. It concludes that Job training is an important component of tourism education curriculum. The highest to lowest percentage of professionals associated with *very high* rating (out of total respondents in individual category of industry professionals) of job training for the benefit of tourism curriculum are: Low Management > Middle Management/Top Management.

Tables 5.88: Management and Job Training

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across job training skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	0	4	10	17	27	58
	0.0%	6.9%	17.2%	29.3%	46.6%	100.0%
	0.0%	50.0%	35.7%	40.5%	57.4%	45.0%
Middle	2	1	12	9	10	34
	5.9%	2.9%	35.3%	26.5%	29.4%	100.0%
	50.0%	12.5%	42.9%	21.4%	21.3%	26.4%
Top	2	3	6	16	10	37
	5.4%	8.1%	16.2%	43.2%	27.0%	100.0%
	50.0%	37.5%	21.4%	38.1%	21.3%	28.7%
Total	4	8	28	42	47	129
	3.1%	6.2%	21.7%	32.6%	36.4%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

D) Level of Management and Research

It was studied from the 5.89 table that to produce ideal tourism professional as well as improvement in tourism education, the emphasis on research in tourism curriculum is needed to *very high* and *high* extent as per the majority from Top Management (32.4 percent) and Low Management (36.2 percent). The Associate Professors have a feeling that a moderate initiative is enough to produce quality human resources. The highest to lowest percentage of professionals associated with *very high* rating (out of total respondents in individual category of industry professionals) of research skills to upgrade tourism curriculum are: Low Management > Top Management > Middle Management

To improve the research component it is necessary to teach research subjects allied to tourism rather than pure research subjects, to establish research head with the collaboration of industry, government and community. Moreover, research problems must be action based, time bound solutions to the problems of stakeholders as well as departmental journal and research publication compulsory at graduate and postgraduate level.

Tables 5.89: Management and Research

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across research skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	3	5	10	21	19	58
	5.2%	8.6%	17.2%	36.2%	32.8%	100.0%
	33.3%	35.7%	33.3%	55.3%	50.0%	45.0%
Middle	3	3	13	8	7	34
	8.8%	8.8%	38.2%	23.5%	20.6%	100.0%
	33.3%	21.4%	43.3%	21.1%	18.4%	26.4%
Top	3	6	7	9	12	37
	8.1%	16.2%	18.9%	24.3%	32.4%	100.0%
	33.3%	42.9%	23.3%	23.7%	31.6%	28.7%
Total	9	14	30	38	38	129
	7.0%	10.9%	23.3%	29.5%	29.5%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

E) Level of Management and Foreign Language

All the levels of management have opinion that Foreign Language Skills need *moderate* level of change to impart quality language skills across the country to give rise to quality professionals. The highest to lowest percentage of professionals associated with *moderate* rating (out of total respondents in individual category of industry professionals) of foreign language to upgrade tourism curriculum are: Low Management > Top management > Middle Management.

Tables 5.90: Management and Foreign Language

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across foreign language skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	4	6	18	13	17	58
	6.9%	10.3%	31.0%	22.4%	29.3%	100.0%
	36.4%	33.3%	41.9%	46.4%	58.6%	45.0%
Middle	3	6	12	7	6	34
	8.8%	17.6%	35.3%	20.6%	17.6%	100.0%
	27.3%	33.3%	27.9%	25.0%	20.7%	26.4%
Top	4	6	13	8	6	37
	10.8%	16.2%	35.1%	21.6%	16.2%	100.0%
	36.4%	33.3%	30.2%	28.6%	20.7%	28.7%
Total	11	18	43	28	29	129
	8.5%	14.0%	33.3%	21.7%	22.5%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

F) Level of Management and Travel Software

The extent of improvement desired for tourism software training is rated as *very high* among all the Low level (37.9 percent) of management and moderate changes by Middle Management (32.4 percent) and Top Management (35.1 percent). The highest to lowest percentage of professionals associated within *very high* rating (out of total respondents in individual category of industry professionals) of tourism software training for the benefit of tourism curriculum are; Low management > Middle management/Top Management.

Table 5.91: Management and Tourism Software

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across Tourism software training skills					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	3	3	9	21	22	58
	5.2%	5.2%	15.5%	36.2%	37.9%	100.0%
	33.3%	20.0%	27.3%	58.3%	61.1%	45.0%
Middle	3	7	11	6	7	34
	8.8%	20.6%	32.4%	17.6%	20.6%	100.0%
	33.3%	46.7%	33.3%	16.7%	19.4%	26.4%
Top	3	5	13	9	7	37
	8.1%	13.5%	35.1%	24.3%	18.9%	100.0%
	33.3%	33.3%	39.4%	25.0%	19.4%	28.7%
Total	9	15	33	36	36	129
	7.0%	11.6%	25.6%	27.9%	27.9%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

G) Level of Management and Digital Skills

It is analysed through the table 5.92 that Low Management (53.4 percent) prefers *very high* new developments in tourism curriculum than Middle Management (32.4 percent) and Top Level Management (29.7 percent). The majority of industry professionals have opinion that current digital skills are not sufficient/outdated and need changes to a very high extent. The highest to lowest percentage of management level associated within *very high* rating are: Low Management > Top Management > Middle Management.

This gap can be bridged through the incorporation of contemporary technology and its practical use in tourism industry, product development, marketing and sustainable development.

Table 5.92: Management and Digital Skills

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across digital skills in tourism					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	3	4	6	14	31	58
	5.2%	6.9%	10.3%	24.1%	53.4%	100.0%
	42.9%	33.3%	21.4%	41.2%	64.6%	45.0%
Middle	2	4	11	10	7	34
	5.9%	11.8%	32.4%	29.4%	20.6%	100.0%
	28.6%	33.3%	39.3%	29.4%	14.6%	26.4%
Top	2	4	11	10	10	37
	5.4%	10.8%	29.7%	27.0%	27.0%	100.0%
	28.6%	33.3%	39.3%	29.4%	20.8%	28.7%
Total	7	12	28	34	48	129
	5.4%	9.3%	21.7%	26.4%	37.2%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

H) Level of Management and Library Resources

It can be inferred from the table that all levels of management feel that existing Library Resources are sufficient and need only *moderate* changes to produce quality human resources. In moderate category, the highest percentage of respondents comprises of Low management and equal percentage from Top and Low Management.

Table 5.93: Management and Library Resources

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across Library resources					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	5	5	22	14	12	58
	8.6%	8.6%	37.9%	24.1%	20.7%	100.0%
	55.6%	20.8%	45.8%	51.9%	57.1%	45.0%
Middle	2	9	13	6	4	34
	5.9%	26.5%	38.2%	17.6%	11.8%	100.0%
	22.2%	37.5%	27.1%	22.2%	19.0%	26.4%
Top	2	10	13	7	5	37
	5.4%	27.0%	35.1%	18.9%	13.5%	100.0%
	22.2%	41.7%	27.1%	25.9%	23.8%	28.7%
Total	9	24	48	27	21	129
	7.0%	18.6%	37.2%	20.9%	16.3%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

I) Level of Management and Academia-Industry Network

The academia-industry interaction is fundamental element of tourism education to produce human resource at par with tourism industry. The fact is proved, as majority (31.0 percent) of tourism professionals and Low Management (44.8 percent) have accepted that to produce quality tourism professionals there is requirement of *very high* improvement in Academia-Industry Networking. The Low management has new entry in to the industry and they realise the gap between academia and industry better than Top Management and Middle Management. The highest to lowest percentage of professionals associated within *very high* rating of AIN for the benefit of tourism curriculum are: Low Management > Top Management > Middle Management

This interaction can be practiced through Alumni meets, conferences, industry lectures, participation of industry professionals in syllabus design and industry sponsored research internship for academicians in industry, networking at regional, national and international levels.

Table 5.94: Management and Academia-Industry Network

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across academia industry networking					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	2	4	11	15	26	58
	3.4%	6.9%	19.0%	25.9%	44.8%	100.0%
	33.3%	28.6%	33.3%	41.7%	65.0%	45.0%
Middle	1	7	9	11	6	34
	2.9%	20.6%	26.5%	32.4%	17.6%	100.0%
	16.7%	50.0%	27.3%	30.6%	15.0%	26.4%
Top	3	3	13	10	8	37
	8.1%	8.1%	35.1%	27.0%	21.6%	100.0%
	50.0%	21.4%	39.4%	27.8%	20.0%	28.7%
Total	6	14	33	36	40	129
	4.7%	10.9%	25.6%	27.9%	31.0%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

J) Level of Management and Student Exchange Programs

There are the sufficient data to prove that SEP are need to be incorporated and existing one need *very high* rate of improvements as per the majority (34.1 percent) of tourism professionals and Low Level Management(51.7 percent).As per the literature

review, political, cultural and geographic understanding about a destination is key to success of tourism professionals. Because a destination, politically stable and liberal, culturally diverse and geographically accessible lead to economic development and wellbeing of host community. It was found during research that only Department of Tourism Studies, Pondicherry University offers student exchange program to the master students but it is limited in numbers. Collaboration with destinations which has exemplary tourism model and university or institutions which have command over specific tourism domain will make it fruitful for the future tourism professionals.

Table 5.95: Management and Student Exchange Program

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across Student Exchange Program					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	4	2	12	10	30	58
	6.9%	3.4%	20.7%	17.2%	51.7%	100.0%
	44.4%	20.0%	34.3%	32.3%	68.2%	45.0%
Middle	1	5	14	9	5	34
	2.9%	14.7%	41.2%	26.5%	14.7%	100.0%
	11.1%	50.0%	40.0%	29.0%	11.4%	26.4%
Top	4	3	9	12	9	37
	10.8%	8.1%	24.3%	32.4%	24.3%	100.0%
	44.4%	30.0%	25.7%	38.7%	20.5%	28.7%
Total	9	10	35	31	44	129
	7.0%	7.8%	27.1%	24.0%	34.1%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Overview: It was found across all levels of management of respondents do not stand in majority for very high change in library resources and Foreign language improvement. Top management is in favour of very high change in FSU and Research content improvement. The Low Management feels that FSU, JT, TST, DS and AIN are the areas which need pre-dominant transformation in existing status to provide quality human resources. Industry-Interaction is the only area favoured across all levels of management for a *very high* change in existing scenario.

5.14 Crosstab Analysis of Academic Designation, Management Levels and Relevance of Tourism Education

It accentuates the opinion of tourism academicians and tourism professionals on the degree up to which tourism education is beneficial for International Peace (IP),

National Image Building (NIB), Sustainable Development (SD), Economic Development (ED) and Environment Conservation (EC).

5.14.1 Academicians

A) Academic designation and international peace

Table 5.96 expresses, among the total respondents, 36.4 percent of total rated the tourism education *highly* relevant to bring international peace at a destination. With regards to professors, majority have opinion that tourism education has *moderate* relevance to bring tourism education. While Assistant professors (53.5 percent) and Associate Professors (37.5 percent) falls in high category. The Guest Faculty (50.0 percent) and Researchers (33.3 percent) opined that tourism education plays a very important role to bring International Peace. In high category, the highest percentage of respondents are Assistant Professors (48.9) although in *very high* category the majority hails from Researchers (33.3).

Table 5.96: Academicians and International Peace

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across international peace					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	0 0.0% 0.0%	-	7 46.7% 17.1%	4 26.7% 8.5%	4 26.7% 10.3%	15 100.0% 11.6%
Associate Professor	0 0.0% 0.0%	-	5 31.2% 12.2%	6 37.5% 12.8%	5 31.2% 12.8%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Assistant Professor	1 2.3% 50.0%	-	10 23.3% 24.4%	23 53.5% 48.9%	9 20.9% 23.1%	43 100.0% 33.3%
Guest Faculty	0 0.0% 0.0%	-	6 37.5% 14.6%	2 12.5% 4.3%	8 50.0% 20.5%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	1 2.6% 50.0%	-	13 33.3% 31.7%	12 30.8% 25.5%	13 33.3% 33.3%	39 100.0% 30.2%
Total	2 1.6% 100.0%	-	41 31.8% 100.0%	47 36.4% 100.0%	39 30.2% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

B) Academic designation and National Image Building

Table 5.97 shows among the total respondents 45.0 percent of total academicians rated the tourism education *very high* that means it is very highly relevant to nation image building. It was also found that Professors (53.3 percent), Associate Professors (37.5 percent), Guest faculty (56.2 percent) and Researchers (51.3 percent) are in favour of very high relevance of tourism education to grow the image of a nation. The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with *very high* rating (out of total respondents in individual category of academicians) of tourism education for the benefit of national image building are: Guest Faculty > Professor > Researcher > Associate professor > Assistant Professor

Table 5.97: Academicians and NIB

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across national image building					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	0	1	3	3	8	15
	0.0%	6.7%	20.0%	20.0%	53.3%	100.0%
	0.0%	25.0%	17.6%	6.1%	13.8%	11.6%
Associate Professor	0	1	4	5	6	16
	0.0%	6.2%	25.0%	31.2%	37.5%	100.0%
	0.0%	25.0%	23.5%	10.2%	10.3%	12.4%
Assistant Professor	1	0	3	24	15	43
	2.3%	0.0%	7.0%	55.8%	34.9%	100.0%
	100.0%	0.0%	17.6%	49.0%	25.9%	33.3%
Guest Faculty	0	1	3	3	9	16
	0.0%	6.2%	18.8%	18.8%	56.2%	100.0%
	0.0%	25.0%	17.6%	6.1%	15.5%	12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	0	1	4	14	20	39
	0.0%	2.6%	10.3%	35.9%	51.3%	100.0%
	0.0%	25.0%	23.5%	28.6%	34.5%	30.2%
Total	1	4	17	49	58	129
	0.8%	3.1%	13.2%	38.0%	45.0%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

C) Academic designation and Sustainable Development

Table 5.98 describes that 43.4 % academicians favour the *very high* relevance of tourism education in sustainable development. The majority of Assistant Professors (55.8 percent) and Guest Faculty (50.0 percent) have opinion that tourism education has very high relevance to development in context of sustainable development. The

Professors (40.0 percent) and Associate Professors (37.5 percent) and Researchers (38.5 percent) also have positive attitude i.e. placed their opinion in *high* category. The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with *very high* rating (out of total respondents in individual category of academicians) of tourism education for the benefit of sustainable development are: Assistant professor > Guest Faculty > Researcher > Professor > Associate professor.

Table 5.98: Academicians and Sustainable Development

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across sustainable development					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	0 0.0% 0.0%	1 6.7% 16.7%	3 20.0% 12.0%	6 40.0% 14.6%	5 33.3% 8.9%	15 100.0% 11.6%
Associate Professor	1 6.2% 100.0%	0 0.0% 0.0%	4 25.0% 16.0%	6 37.5% 14.6%	5 31.2% 8.9%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Assistant Professor	0 0.0% 0.0%	1 2.3% 16.7%	7 16.3% 28.0%	11 25.6% 26.8%	24 55.8% 42.9%	43 100.0% 33.3%
Guest Faculty	0 0.0% 0.0%	0 0.0% 0.0%	5 31.2% 20.0%	3 18.8% 7.3%	8 50.0% 14.3%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	0 0.0% 0.0%	4 10.3% 66.7%	6 15.4% 24.0%	15 38.5% 36.6%	14 35.9% 25.0%	39 100.0% 30.2%
Total	1 0.8% 100.0%	6 4.7% 100.0%	25 19.4% 100.0%	41 31.8% 100.0%	56 43.4% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

D) Academic designation and Economic Development

It was found that 48.1 percent respondents accepted that tourism education has *very high* role in economic development. The designation wise categories of academicians has strong belief that tourism education is a keystone to bring economic development. The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with *very high* rating (out of total respondents in individual category of academicians) of tourism education for the benefit of economic development are: Guest Faculty > Associate professor > Assistant professor > Professor > Researcher.

Table 5.99: Academicians and Economic Development

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across economic development					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	-	0 0.0% 0.0%	5 33.3% 17.2%	3 20.0% 8.1%	7 46.7% 11.3%	15 100.0% 11.6%
Associate Professor	-	0 0.0% 0.0%	3 18.8% 10.3%	5 31.2% 13.5%	8 50.0% 12.9%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Assistant Professor	-	0 0.0% 0.0%	8 18.6% 27.6%	14 32.6% 37.8%	21 48.8% 33.9%	43 100.0% 33.3%
Guest Faculty	-	0 0.0% 0.0%	5 31.2% 17.2%	2 12.5% 5.4%	9 56.2% 14.5%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	-	1 2.6% 100%	8 20.5% 27.6%	13 33.3% 35.1%	17 43.6% 27.4%	39 100.0% 30.2%
Total	-	1 0.8% 100.0%	29 22.5% 100.0%	37 28.7% 100.0%	62 48.1% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

E) Academic designation and Environment Conservation

The majority of total respondents as well as Assistant professors (53.5 percent), Guest Faculty (43.8 percent), Researchers (43.6 percent) and Associate Professors (37.5 percent) believe that tourism education is one of the key players to fix environmental issues. The highest to lowest percentage of academicians associated with *very high* rating (out of total respondents in individual category of academicians) of tourism education for the benefit of economic development are: Assistant professor > Guest Faculty > Researcher > Associate professor > Professor

Table 5.100: Academician and Environment Conservation

Tourism Academicians	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across environment conservation					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Professor	0 0.0% 0.0%	1 6.7% 16.7%	6 40.0% 17.6%	3 20.0% 10.0%	5 33.3% 8.6%	15 100.0% 11.6%
Associate Professor	1 6.2% 100.0%	0 0.0% 0.0%	5 31.2% 14.7%	4 25.0% 13.3%	6 37.5% 10.3%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Assistant Professor	0 0.0% 0.0%	3 7.0% 50.0%	9 20.9% 26.5%	8 18.6% 26.7%	23 53.5% 39.7%	43 100.0% 33.3%
Guest Faculty	0 0.0% 0.0%	0 0.0% 0.0%	7 43.8% 20.6%	2 12.5% 6.7%	7 43.8% 12.1%	16 100.0% 12.4%
Research Scholar (Tourism)	0 0.0% 0.0%	2 5.1% 33.3%	7 17.9% 20.6%	13 33.3% 43.3%	17 43.6% 29.3%	39 100.0% 30.2%
Total	1 0.8% 100.0%	6 4.7% 100.0%	34 26.4% 100.0%	30 23.3% 100.0%	58 45.0% 100.0%	129 100.0% 100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Overview: The Guest faculty assume that tourism education is *very highly* relevant to Peace, National Image, Sustainable Development, Economic development and Environment Conservation. However, all level of management perceive that tourism education has towering relevance for economic development.

5.14.2 Tourism professionals

A) Tourism professionals, tourism education and International peace

The Top Management (32.4 percent) and Middle Management (32.4 percent) have similar views as of majority (33.3 percent) of the respondents have i.e. opinion as a whole talks about the moderate relevance to tourism education. The Low Management (36.2 percent) differs in opinion than Top Management and Middle Management. The highest to lowest percentage of professionals associated with *moderate* category are; Low management > Top management > Middle management.

Table 5.101: Tourism professionals and International Peace

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across international peace					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	1	0	20	21	16	58
	1.7%	0.0%	34.5%	36.2%	27.6%	100.0%
	12.5%	0.0%	46.5%	55.3%	53.3%	45.0%
Middle	4	7	11	8	4	34
	11.8%	20.6%	32.4%	23.5%	11.8%	100.0%
	50.0%	70.0%	25.6%	21.1%	13.3%	26.4%
Top	3	3	12	9	10	37
	8.1%	8.1%	32.4%	24.3%	27.0%	100.0%
	37.5%	30.0%	27.9%	23.7%	33.3%	28.7%
Total	8	10	43	38	30	129
	6.2%	7.8%	33.3%	29.5%	23.3%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

B) Tourism professionals, tourism education and National Image Building

The opinion of majority of total respondents and Top Management (37.8 percent) is scattered over *very high* and *high* categories; Low Management (46.6 percent) and Middle Management (44.1 percent) have opined that the relevance of tourism education for National Image Building falls in *very high* and *moderate* categories. The highest to lowest percentage of professionals associated with *very high* rating (out of total respondents in individual category of industry professionals) of tourism education for the benefit of national image building are: Low Management > Top Management > Middle Management

Table 5.102: Tourism professionals and National Image Building

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across national image building					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	0	1	9	21	27	58
	0.0%	1.7%	15.5%	36.2%	46.6%	100.0%
	0.0%	33.3%	30.0%	45.7%	58.7%	45.0%
Middle	2	1	15	11	5	34
	5.9%	2.9%	44.1%	32.4%	14.7%	100.0%
	50.0%	33.3%	50.0%	23.9%	10.9%	26.4%
Top	2	1	6	14	14	37
	5.4%	2.7%	16.2%	37.8%	37.8%	100.0%
	50.0%	33.3%	20.0%	30.4%	30.4%	28.7%
Total	4	3	30	46	46	129
	3.1%	2.3%	23.3%	35.7%	35.7%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

C) Tourism professionals, tourism education and Sustainable Development

The principles sustainability maximizes the opportunities and minimises the negative effects of tourism (Posner, 2014). Hence Sustainable Development is among the most demanded parameter of infrastructure development across the globe. It is found in the study that majority (39.5 percent) of total tourism professionals, Top Management (56.8 percent) and Low Management (39.7 percent) considered that promotion of tourism education can be one of the ‘most catalytic’ tools to achieve Sustainable Development. The highest to lowest percentage of professionals associated with *very high* rating (out of total respondents in individual category of industry professionals) of tourism education for the benefit of national image building are: Top management > Low management > Middle management

Table 5.103: Tourism professionals and Sustainable Development

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across sustainable development					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	0	0	12	23	23	58
	0.0%	0.0%	20.7%	39.7%	39.7%	100.0%
	0.0%	0.0%	46.2%	48.9%	45.1%	45.0%
Middle	1	1	12	13	7	34
	2.9%	2.9%	35.3%	38.2%	20.6%	100.0%
	50.0%	33.3%	46.2%	27.7%	13.7%	26.4%
Top	1	2	2	11	21	37
	2.7%	5.4%	5.4%	29.7%	56.8%	100.0%
	50.0%	66.7%	7.7%	23.4%	41.2%	28.7%
Total	2	3	26	47	51	129
	1.6%	2.3%	20.2%	36.4%	39.5%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

D) Tourism professionals, tourism education and Economic Development

Tourism is a keystone to economic growth, locally and globally (OECD, 2020). The results shows that Top Management (70.3 percent), Low management (55.2 percent) and majority (51.2 percent) of tourism professionals have marked tourism education *very highly* relevant to bring economic development to a destination. Tourism brings employment, export revenue and foreign exchange (OECD, 2016). In the *very high* category, the descending order of consensus about the relevance of tourism education to bring economic development is: Low management > Top management > Middle management.

Table 5.104: Tourism professionals and Economic Development

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across economic development					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	0	0	7	19	32	58
	0.0%	0.0%	12.1%	32.8%	55.2%	100.0%
	0.0%	0.0%	31.8%	52.8%	48.5%	45.0%
Middle	2	2	11	11	8	34
	5.9%	5.9%	32.4%	32.4%	23.5%	100.0%
	66.7%	100.0%	50.0%	30.6%	12.1%	26.4%
Top	1	0	4	6	26	37
	2.7%	0.0%	10.8%	16.2%	70.3%	100.0%
	33.3%	0.0%	18.2%	16.7%	39.4%	28.7%
Total	3	2	22	36	66	129
	2.3%	1.6%	17.1%	27.9%	51.2%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

E) Tourism professionals, tourism education and Environment Conservation

Tourism brings finance for environment initiatives (The Cleanweb Initiative, 2018). It is the tourism education which can impart awareness about ‘code of conduct’ about different tourism stakeholders at a destination. It was observed that Top Management (51.4 percent), Low Management (58.6 percent) and majority (47.3 percent) of respondents assemble their opinions around the *very high* relevance of tourism education for Environment Conservation. The highest percentage of respondents in very high category belongs to Low Management (55.7).

Table 5.105: Tourism professionals and Environment Conservation

Level of management	Cross tabulation distribution of designation across environment conservation					Total
	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	
Low	0	0	9	15	34	58
	0.0%	0.0%	15.5%	25.9%	58.6%	100.0%
	0.0%	0.0%	32.1%	42.9%	55.7%	45.0%
Middle	2	0	15	9	8	34
	5.9%	0.0%	44.1%	26.5%	23.5%	100.0%
	66.7%	0.0%	53.6%	25.7%	13.1%	26.4%
Top	1	2	4	11	19	37
	2.7%	5.4%	10.8%	29.7%	51.4%	100.0%
	33.3%	100.0%	14.3%	31.4%	31.1%	28.7%
Total	3	2	28	35	61	129
	2.3%	1.6%	21.7%	27.1%	47.3%	100.0%
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Primary data through questionnaire.

Overview: Tourism education has stratospheric relevance to National Image Building, Sustainable Development, Economic Development and Environment Conservation as per the opinion of Top and Low Management. Although, none of the management level has a feeling that tourism education is immoderately relevant to peace building at a tourism destination.

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